

CEE2ACT

**Empowering the Central and
Eastern European Countries to Develop
Bioeconomy Strategies and Action Plans**

**Set of sustainability criteria and indicators for bioeconomy
implementation**

Funded by
the European Union

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¹ PU = Public

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

There are several measures and options that can contribute to the implementation of bioeconomy from a bottom-up perspective. The question arise which measures are feasible for bioeconomy implementation in a sustainable way considering the respective national background. The evaluation methodology described in this report targets to track economic, environmental, and social imperatives towards a sustainable bioeconomy. These objectives need to be represented by appropriate criteria that are made measurable by indicators. The report explains the process to select appropriate criteria and indicators for the evaluation of options to implement bioeconomy in MS countries. By applying a multi-actor approach, it is foreseen that CEE2ACT partners as well as external stakeholders are included in the selection process.

The method for selecting criteria and indicators follows a stepwise approach. First, a list of indicators and criteria was compiled from literature, EU projects and the EU bioeconomy monitoring dashboard. Then a pre-selection was carried out based on feasibility for the evaluation aim. This process was accompanied by several discussion rounds in small groups as well as with the entire CEE2ACT consortium via a webinar. Finally, a set of indicators was selected for an online survey to collect the level of measurability from 1 (not at all measurable) to 5 (very likely to be measurable) and the level of importance from 1 (not at all important) to 5 (very important) for each indicator from partners and stakeholders. Participants also had the opportunity to not judge the levels, if they lack the knowledge. Based on the survey results, a set of indicators and criteria was finally extracted.

Around 477 indicators were collected from literature and other sources. Most of them related to the economic imperative, followed by the environmental and social imperative. This extensive list was shortened by merging indicators with the same mid-point, by removing duplicates (indicators with similar goals were discussed in small groups to find out which indicator is more suitable) and by removing indicators that are not suitable for the evaluation of bioeconomy implementation in the current context. From the extensive list, a total of 61 were pre-selected and grouped to the following criteria: eco-friendly bioeconomy, eco-friendly agriculture, eco-friendly forestry, eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries, bioeconomy acceptance and recognition, fair and healthy society, biomass availability, competitiveness, contribution to economic development, employment and country's resilience.

In total 70 out of 128 participants completed the online survey (dropout rate: 45%). The majority of the participants were stakeholders (63%), from Poland, Greece, Slovakia, Romania, Bulgaria and Serbia. Most of the participants work in Research and Development, followed by non-governmental organisations and voluntary organisations, small and medium enterprises, public service and higher education. The biggest sectors were agriculture, food and feed, forestry, and ecosystem services. Indicators rated by the level of importance ranged from "Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption" with an average level of 4.5 to "Gender equality" with

an average level of 3.2. Indicators above the average level of importance of 4 were selected. This reduced the number of indicators from 61 to 28. Almost all criteria are covered except for eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries. A further selection regarding the level of measurability is foreseen in the next step of the project. This deliverable though presents a thorough basis for future decisions, which might be still expanded if required

DISCLAIMER

The CEE2ACT project is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

1. Introduction

Position in the CEE2ACT project

The evaluation within workpackage 2 (WP2) is situated in the project CEE2ACT next to separate evaluation works in other workpackages, for details see Table 1.

Each of the evaluation frameworks have different aims and thus different indicators are foreseen for quantifying corresponding criteria.

Table 1: Evaluation concepts within CEE2ACT

CEE2ACT Workpackage (WP)	Aim of the evaluation	Corresponding deliverables	Due Date
WP2	Evaluation of options to measure the implementation of bioeconomy	D2.2 "Set of sustainability criteria and indicators for bioeconomy implementation" and D2.3 "Report on sustainability assessment of the bioeconomy concepts"	Dec 2023 (M16) Aug 2024 (M24)
WP3	Evaluation of stakeholder engagement	D3.3 Impact evaluation report	Aug 2025 (M36)
WP5	Evaluation of knowledge transfer	D5.2 Evaluation and recommendations from CEE and EU perspective	July 2025 (M35)

Aim of the evaluation

The overarching goal of the project is to stipulate bioeconomy in countries with poor or no bioeconomy strategy in place. As part of the project, questions arise on how to implement bioeconomy, which measures are feasible for bioeconomy implementation and which measure to consider in an action plan of a bioeconomy strategy. Bioeconomy is expected to contribute to all 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and in particular to SDGs 1 and 2 (Zero Hunger & Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) and SDG 13 (Climate Action).

There are several solutions (hereafter called 'options') that can contribute to an implementation of bioeconomy from a bottom-up perspective in different member states (MS) in the EU. Therefore, the main questions to be answered in WP2 are:

- 1 Which specific measures to implement bioeconomy (referred hereafter to “options”) are the most sustainable to implement in your country?
- 2 Which framework conditions are necessary to make options sustainable in your country?

According to Mubareka et al. (2023), the bioeconomy is “a set of intertwined interconnections of various degrees of strength and with directionality” and thus challenging to quantify. However, we should “think about how to identify the most critical nodes and connections in order to focus on indicators in those areas, or to attribute weights to indicators”. Therefore, the clear benefit of the evaluation is to improve understanding of interactions within the bioeconomy.

Evaluation framework and definitions

The objective of the evaluation is the implementation of a sustainable bioeconomy. The sub-objectives are therefore based on "triple bottom line" (Elkington 1994) to track economic, environmental and social imperatives towards a sustainable bioeconomy. These objectives need to be represented by appropriate criteria that are made measurable by indicators. Therefore, criteria and indicators have to be found for each of the sustainability pillars. To ensure sustainable bioeconomy strategies the evaluation of options must be carried out against the respective national framework conditions. This applies to both national circumstances and political preferences. Different stakeholders have different preferences that needs to be considered as well.

With this in mind, all options, criteria, indicators and stakeholder preferences are combined in a multi-criteria-decision-analysis (MCDA). The process and structure of a MCDA are both shown in Figure 1. Stakeholders, that are persons working in the bioeconomy field but beyond the CEE2ACT consortium, are foreseen to be included in the selection of indicators as well as in the interpretation of results to enable an understanding of trade-offs and a classification of options for future action plans of the national bioeconomy strategy.

Figure 1: Process and structure of a multi-criteria decision analysis (MCDA) based on Kühmaier (2023)

To ensure a common understanding of frequently used terms for evaluation processes, the most important terms are described in more detail in Table 2.

Table 2: Glossary of terms used in the evaluation

Terms	Definition	Examples
Options	Options refer to measures or actions that are necessary to implement bioeconomy in a country; referred also to bioeconomy-related options or bioeconomy options	<i>agricultural waste for biogas production biodegradable plastic mulch films multi-feedstock biorefinery processes microalgae for biofuels food residues for food or feed ingredients</i>
Criteria	Criteria is derived from the goals. They describe activities and measures as the key to achieving the goals	<i>Energy efficiency Gender equality Investment</i>
Indicator	Indicators are defined for criteria that specify observable characteristics of target achievements. The indicators show if, and to what extent, the target is met.	<i>GHG emissions in kgCO₂e Share of women with jobs in % Jobs created in Full Time Equivalentents</i>
Normalization	The value of the indicators needs to be transferred into normalized values	<i>By ordinal scale</i>
Weighting	Weighting of criteria	<i>By expert consultation (individual or group consultation)</i>

Procedure of the evaluation

By applying a multi-actor approach, it is foreseen that other CEE2ACT partners as well as external stakeholders will be included in addition to the WP2 core team. Figure 2 shows the steps of the evaluation process and the steps where CEE2ACT partners and stakeholders are foreseen to be involved.

Stakeholder opinions and preferences will feed into the evaluation methodology, which is why stakeholders are foreseen to participate in the selection of criteria and indicators as well as in the selection of options for evaluation. CEE2ACT partners will also assist in the collection of data for the assessment. The calculations as well as the normalization of results will be conducted by the WP2 core team, established by University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences Vienna (BOKU), the Institute of Soil Science and Plant Cultivation (IUNG), Collaborating Centre on Sustainable Consumption and Production (CSCP) and Stichting Wageningen Research (WR).

Figure 2: Procedure of the evaluation within WP2

2. Method of the selection of criteria and indicators

The set of criteria and indicators for the evaluation of bioeconomy implementation is developed in a step-wise approach, see Figure 3.

Figure 3: Procedure for the selection of indicators and criteria

Step 1: Compilation of a list of indicators

The initial point of the collection was the decision by IUNG, that the primary sources of knowledge would be the outcome of two projects coordinated by the department of Bioeconomy and Systems Analysis in IUNG. The first was BioEcon New Strategies on Bio-Economy in Poland, funded with EU from Horizon 2020 and completed on December 31, 2020. The project focused on the estimation of economic potential of biomass for the most promising bio-based value chains along with the promotion of sustainable growth, which is significantly important in addressing environmental problems, economic challenges or social inequalities. IUNG established an interdisciplinary research unit that specializes in this type of research and analysis, which is in operation after the project's completion. The main goal of the project was to improve the organization and management of research, address issues related to research and innovation strategy, develop cooperation with policy makers and stakeholders, improve research excellence in the areas of bioeconomy and systems analysis, and to promote bioeconomy in the region. Another important project on which the work was based was Advancing Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Central and Eastern European Countries: BIOEASTsUP, funded by EU from Horizon 2020 and completed on March 31, 2023. The project was about accelerating the development of the bioeconomy in Central and Eastern Europe. In order to be able to talk about the transition of Central and Eastern European countries to a sustainable circular bioeconomy, it is necessary to involve a number of actors, which were to be identified in this project. The project aimed to

provide support for the development of the bioeconomy at the national, macro-regional and European levels. The project activities involved 11 countries in Central and Eastern Europe, and its mission was to respond to the challenges of national and regional strategy, as well as research and innovation.

The next step, after reviewing the outcomes of the aforementioned projects aiming at capitalizing the acquired knowledge from them, as well as exploiting expertise, was to research indicators in relevant tools available free of charge. Scanning in Elsevier / ScienceDirect and Google Scholar, we identified another corpus of articles that contained information on indicators used to monitor the bioeconomy. The two sources with the largest article base were:

- Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy. Overview and a proposed way forward, Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations, Rome, 2019. The report is a component of FAO's Towards Sustainable Bioeconomy Guidelines (SBG) project. The project is based on work on non-food biomass products and biotechnology. Project activities are also related to the work on sustainability indicators, which should provide technical assistance to countries and stakeholders in developing and monitoring a sustainable bioeconomy by developing indicators in line with the Aspirational Principles for a Sustainable Bioeconomy and the criteria put forward by the International Working Group on a Sustainable Bioeconomy.
- Implementation of the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System dashboards, (Kilsedar, C., et al., 2021; Kilsedar, C., et al. 2023; Giuntoli, J., et al., 2020)

The following articles were used in the development and were found through search engines based on keywords such as 'bioeconomy criteria' or 'bioeconomy indicators' or 'bioeconomy monitoring' or 'bioeconomy assessment'. Through all these activities, a large group of articles were identified, from which the following articles were selected (see Table 3):

Table 3: Scientific sources from which potential indicators to be used have been mapped

Nr	Title	Author	Year	Source
1	Bioeconomy: tapping natural and human resources to achieve sustainability	Diaz-Chavez, et al. (Editor)	2019	Stockholm Env. Institute Link p. 29-31 Link p. 19-24
2	Development of the Circular Bioeconomy: Drivers and Indicators	Kardung, M. et al.	2021	Sustainability, 2021,13, 413 Link
3	Socioeconomic Indicators to Monitor the EU's Bioeconomy in Transition	Ronzon, T. et al.	2018	Sustainability 2018, 10, 1745 Link
4	Forest bioeconomy- a new scope for Sustainability indicators. From Science to Policy 4.	Wolfslehner, B. et al.	2016	European Forest Institute Link
5	A New Socio-economic Indicator To Measure the Performance of Bioeconomy Sectors in Europe	D'Adamo, I. et al.	2020	Ecological Economics Volume 176 Link

6	Bioeconomy mapping indicators and methodology. Case study about forest sector in Latvia	Blumberga, D. et al.	2017	Science Direct, Energy Procedia 128 p.363-367
7	Environmental aspects of the implementation of bioeconomy in the Baltic Sea Region: An input-output approach	Brizga, J. et al.	2019	Journal of Cleaner Production Link
8	Indicators to monitor and evaluate the sustainability of bioeconomy, Overview and a proposed way forward	Bracco, S. et al.	2019	Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations
9	Monitoring Bioeconomy Transitions with Economic-Environmental and Innovation Indicators: Addressing Data Gaps in the Short Term	Jander, W. et al.	2020	Sustainability 2020, 12(11), 4683 Link
10	Sustainability Performance of National Bio-Economies	Biber-Freudenberger, L. et al.	2018	Sustainability 2020, 12, 4683 Link
11	Socioeconomic Indicators to Monitor Norway's Bioeconomy in Transition	Capasso, M. and Klitkou, A.	2020	Sustainability 2020, 12(8), 3173 Link
12	Measuring the importance of the bioeconomy in Germany: Concept and illustration	Efken, J. et al.	2016	NJAS: Wageningen Journal of Life Sciences, 77:1, pp.9-17
13	Conceptualization of an Indicator System for Assessing the Sustainability of the Bioeconomy	Egenolf, V. and Bringezu, S.	2019	Sustainability 2019, 11(2), 443 Link
14	The Role of Bioeconomy Sectors and Natural Resources in EU Economies: A Social Accounting Matrix-Based Analysis Approach	Fuentes-Saguar, P. et al.	2017	Sustainability 2017, 9(12), 2383 Link
15	Assesing the Potentials of Bioeconomy Sectors in Poland Employing Input-Output Modeling	Loizou, E.; Jurga, P. Rozakis, S. and Faber, A.	2019	Sustainability 2019, 11(3), 594 Link
16	Analysis on Bioeconomy's Contribution to GDP: Evidence from Japan	Wen, X. et al.	2019	Sustainability 2019, 11(3), 712 Link
17	When Do Supply Chains Strengthen Biological and Cultural Diversity? Methods and Indicators for the Socio-Biodiversity Bioeconomy	Macchione Saes, M. S. et al.	2023	Sustainability 2023, 15(10), 8053 Link
18	Methodological assessment framework of Socioeconomic systems' bio-economic transformation management	Vostriakova, V.	2023	Journal of Vasyl Stefanyk Precarpathian National University, p.33-44

The selection of relevant criteria/indicators is implemented as described below. First of all, individual indicators were evaluated to see whether they met the following characteristics: validity; widely accepted; accessible data; clearly defined and standardized; performance based ; easily communicable.

Step 2: Pre-selection of indicators by WP2 team

The exhaustive list of indicators is shortened to a manageable number by:

- * Merging indicators with the same mid-point (e.g. 'climate change', 'Global Warming Potential')
- * Choosing among indicators with the same or similar meaning/goal: Indicators with a similar goal are discussed to find out which indicator is more suitable
- * Removing indicators that are estimated to be not suitable for the evaluation of bioeconomy implementation

This process demands intensive discussion rounds via online meetings and e-mail exchange between partners of the core group in charge of the evaluation of bioeconomy implementation, that are BOKU and IUNG.

Firstly, each partner defines indicators that can be removed. If a mutual agreement between partners of removable indicators is met, then the indicator is excluded from the list. If no mutual agreement is reached, the indicator is discussed in an online meeting or by commenting in the file in the second step. This process is repeated several times to reach a desired number of indicators that are feasible to show to partners and stakeholders (about 60 indicators).

The remaining indicators were grouped into specific sub-objectives. These pre-selected indicators were shown in the online survey in Step 3.

Step 3: Selection of indicators by partners and stakeholders

The selection process covered a webinar to inform partners about the evaluation process and an online survey to collect opinions about the evaluation criteria from partners and stakeholders.

Partners are informed in a **webinar** about the aim of the evaluation (Why do we want to evaluate? What do we want to evaluate?), about the evaluation process (How do we foresee to evaluate?) and their level of contribution (Where is the contribution needed?). The webinar also includes swapping break-out sessions to discuss in small groups each evaluation pillar in a greater detail. The webinar (screenshot Figure 4) took place at November 2023 via Zoom. Webinar slides are attached in the Annex.

CEE2ACT Webinar on the "Selection of criteria and indicators for the evaluation"
8th Nov 2023

Objectives:

- to introduce a suitable list of indicators for the evaluation
- to explain the process of selecting and weighting of the indicators

Zoom link:
<https://bokuvienna.zoom.us/j/62153495577>

CET	AGENDA
10.30	Welcome (BOKU, G. Obersteiner)
	Evaluation framework in CEE2ACT (BOKU, S. Scherhauser)
	Introduction to the criteria list (IUNG, S. Rozakis & P. Jurga)
11.00	Group discussions on suitability of criteria (10 min each) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Environmental impacts - Social impacts - Economic impacts
11.40	Explanation of the process of weighting the criteria and Wrap-up
12.00	End of the webinar

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Figure 4: Agenda and objectives of the webinar for partners, organised on the 8th November 2023

An **online survey** was established to collect the opinions of partners and stakeholders about the level of importance (from 1 “not very important” to 5 meaning “very important”) for each indicator and the level of measurability (from 1 “not very likely to be measurable” to 5 “very likely to be measurable”). The establishment of a user-friendly survey was required to generate a high response rate. LimeSurvey (screenshot, see Figure 5) was chosen as a tool since it has a user-friendly interface and allows for enough flexibility for asking open, closed and etc. questions.

Additionally, it was possible to add missing indicators directly in the online survey by partners and stakeholder.

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CEE2ACT Survey

on the

Selection of criteria & indicators

for the

Evaluation of bioeconomy-related options

on country level

Dear Participant,

you are invited to take part in the activities of the project "CEE2ACT- Empowering the Central and Eastern European Countries to Develop Circular Bioeconomy Strategies and Action Plans", funded under the Horizon Europe framework by the European Commission.

Purpose of this survey is to collect expert knowledge and estimations on the selection of criteria and indicators that is feasible for the assessment of measures stipulating bioeconomy.

Your expert opinion is of high relevance for our work.

This is an anonymous survey! Your answers will not be associated with you personally or with your institution.

No personal information about you is stored in the survey responses unless a question explicitly asks for it.

Please read and accept the informed consent to take part at this survey.

Figure 5: First page of the online survey for partners and stakeholders; submitted on 27th November 2023

Step 4: Defining the “set”

The results of the online survey are taken to show the set of indicators. Indicators that are rated with high importance (more than average across all indicators) and high measurability (more than average across all indicators).

3. Collection of criteria and indicators related to bioeconomy

The outcomes of the previously described indicator research procedure is described in the following chapters, categorized according to main sources.

Criteria and indicators from literature

The following table summarises the initial number of indicators allocated to the three sustainability pillars including a preliminary division into subgroups corresponding to the EU bioeconomy strategy main goals.

Table 4: Initial number of indicators per section and main goals

	Economic criteria	Environmental criteria	Social criteria	Total
Climate change	3	35	1	39
Competitiveness and creating job	147	4	79	230
Food security	3	1	19	23
Natural Resources and Sustainability	39	121	13	173
Non-renewable Resources	2	10	-	12
Total	194	171	112	447

Table 4 shows that the initial number of indicators was 477. The largest number of indicators belongs to the economic section, with 194 indicators, whereas 171 indicators are allocated to the environmental section. In the subgroups classified according to the EU BE strategic goals, by far the largest number of indicators was in the section competitiveness and employment with 230 indicators, and in natural resources and sustainable development with 173 indicators. The number of indicators was reduced to 180 criteria/indicators. Duplicate records, irrelevant after content analysis or those that were deemed difficult to measure were removed. A pivot table was updated with the reduced number of indicators. It is still worth noting the large number of criteria/indicators pertaining to the categories (economy/competitiveness-employment (in this case, 80 indicators); economy-natural resources and sustainability (12 indicators) and environment-natural resources and sustainability (40 indicators). The number of indicators in the above-mentioned pairs has significantly decreased as it previously was 147, 39 and 121, respectively, but it was still deemed too large. In the next step, a qualitative selection had to be made to reduce these numbers to a range of 5-10 indicators, so that the total number of criteria fell below 50.

Criteria and indicators from EU funded projects

Beside CEE2ACT, other projects in Europe are dealing with the bio-economy topics and many of them are part of The European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet). This network is an alliance of 150 EU funded projects and initiatives dealing with bio-economy promotion, communication and support. Each project has different a focus in terms of bioeconomy as well as different target regions, including some that are dealing with the research of optimized indicators and categories for bioeconomy. Findings from such projects were considered for this workpackage, such as the outcome from Power4Bio <https://power4bio.eu/>, BioMonitor <https://biomonitor.eu/>, and Star-ProBio <http://www.star-probio.eu/>.

In the **Power4Bio project** report D.2.2: Key performance indicators to evaluate regional bioeconomies the development of a methodology for assessing short- and medium-term bioeconomy strategies in European regions is discussed. The methodology includes a list of key factors and performance indicators, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation and comparison of proposed actions. The factors and indicators are designed with consideration for regional aspects, with feedback from POWER4BIO regional representatives contributing to their refinement. The indicators cater to various stakeholders, such as policy makers, research personnel, consultants, and companies involved in bioeconomy strategy development. The assessment of bioeconomy evolution covers interdisciplinary topics across eight categories, including resources, infrastructure, research, market/economic aspects, transition, support/governance/policy, funding, and social/environmental aspects. The diversity of participating regions enriches the indicators, ensuring a broad scope that addresses different experiences and realities. The developed indicators will facilitate communication between regions and technical experts in POWER4BIO, providing a common reference. The document emphasizes the importance of addressing both general and specific challenges, representing geographical dimensions and technical/non-technical barriers.

While the current list of indicators is considered a solid basis, the document acknowledges the potential need for additional or adjusted indicators during the project's execution. The document is deemed crucial for the overall project, framing the collection and use of information across all tasks in POWER4BIO. Future tasks will involve a thorough analysis of how to use the indicators, initiating discussions and analysis.

The **STAR-ProBio** Deliverable D2.2, "Selection of environmental indicators and impact categories for the life cycle assessment of bio-based products." outlines the findings of STAR-ProBio Task 2.3, which focuses on selecting life cycle impact assessment (LCIA), standardized environmental indicators, and impact categories for conducting environmental life cycle assessments (E-LCA) of bio-based products. The approach involves a two-step process:

- **Impact Categories Selection:** The report defines a set of hierarchized criteria for selecting impact categories. This leads to a list of impact categories grouped within clusters (categories with similarities in impact pathways) determined in D2.1.
- **Methodologies Selection):** The report establishes hierarchized criteria for selecting methodologies, resulting in the choice of a specific methodology for each impact category.

The chosen assessment criteria include:

- **Ability to Compare:** The ability to compare bio-based materials and compare them against conventional petrochemical products.
- **Scientific Relevance:** The scientific importance of the impact category.
- **Political and Social Priority:** The priority given to an impact category in political and social contexts.
- **Reliability and Robustness:** The reliability and robustness of the assessment methodology.

- Representativeness: How well the impact category represents the environmental impact of bio-based materials.
- Stakeholder and Market Perception: How stakeholders and the market perceive the impact category.

Based on these criteria, a set of 11 indicators and associated models is recommended for the environmental assessment of bio-based materials. These indicators cover a range of environmental aspects and are proposed to be tested through STAR-ProBio case studies. The indicators include acidification, particulate matter, global warming potential BIO, potentially affected biodiversity, terrestrial eutrophication, freshwater eutrophication, human toxicity (cancer), land use (soil quality index), soil erosion, fossil resources depletion, and water scarcity.

The deliverable of the **BioMonitor** project “D1.1: Framework for measuring the size and development of the bioeconomy” outlines the development of a conceptual analysis framework for quantifying and analyzing the development of the EU bioeconomy. The scope of the framework, based on the European Commission's definition, encompasses biomass-producing activities, conventional biomass processing, and novel biomass processing. However, the focus for methodological improvements is on bio-based production due to the lack of existing data and the anticipation of rapid and volatile developments in related sub-sectors.

The framework considers the influence of innovation, policies, strategies, and legislation on the bioeconomy's development, with the understanding that these factors can be implemented at different governance levels. New indicators have been proposed to monitor these aspects.

Sustainability is a key consideration, especially in terms of the environmental dimension, and the framework incorporates strategies from the circular economy, such as the recycling of bio-based products. The set of indicators aims to measure the circularity of the bioeconomy and its contribution to Sustainable Development Goals.

Recognizing the complexity and resource limitations, the framework acknowledges challenges in tracking all emerging bio-based products. Selection criteria for inclusion in statistics involve adjusting data collection procedures and conducting sound market analysis. The BioMonitor project scope does not involve systematic data collection but focuses on developing methodologies for collecting and improving data.

Some of the indicators are similar in each project such as greenhouse gas reduction as these indicators are from basic importance for assessing bioeconomy activities but with different level of granularity. The majority of indicators found in the projects were already included in the considerations for CEE2ACT. Other indicators were targeted to the aim of the specific project and are not that relevant for CEE2ACT terms, as the focus within the CEE2ACT project is to identify indicators for the assessment of feasible measures for bioeconomy implementation in targeted countries. Yet, some indicators were not yet considered and further on integrated in the preliminary indicator list, that was sent to all partners and stakeholders for final selection of indicators.

Criteria and indicators from the EU dashboard Bioeconomy and Monitoring System

Indicators of the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System (BMS) are aligned to the EU bioeconomy strategy objectives:

- (1) ensuring food and nutrition security,
- (2) managing natural resources sustainably,
- (3) reducing dependence on non-renewable, unsustainable resources,
- (4) mitigating and adapting to climate change,
- (5) strengthening European competitiveness and creating jobs.

These five objectives are split into 19 sub-objectives (2nd level) that again consist of 49 key components (3rd level) that can be measured by 203 indicators (4th level). In the current dashboard data is shown for only a limited number of indicators (87). The number of gaps in indicators and the quality of data are reported as main limitations for the current EU BMS (Mubareka et al., 2023).

The indicators of the EU BMS are only conditionally applicable for the evaluation of options in CEE2ACT as the purpose of the evaluation is different. The aim of the EU Bioeconomy Monitoring System is to fulfil the need of a holistic policy monitoring framework at European level whereas the aim within CEE2ACT is to evaluate bioeconomy implementation from the bottom-up with a national focus. The evaluation in CEE2ACT is more related to a data-driven approach than holistic approach. Nevertheless, some indicators (such as value added, biomass production, etc.) are used as well.

4. Pre-selected criteria and indicators

From the extensive list of more than 400 indicators, a total of 61 were pre-selected and grouped into specific groups (sub-objectives). Table 5 shows an overview of the number of indicators per sub-objective. 27 indicators were selected for the environmental perspective consisting of the sub-objectives eco-friendly bioeconomy (6 indicators), eco-friendly agriculture (11), eco-friendly forestry (7) and eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries (3). 11 indicators were allocated to the social perspective containing bioeconomy acceptance/recognition (5) as well as fair and healthy society (6). 23 indicators were defined for the economic perspective with biomass availability (5), competitiveness (8), contribution to economic development (4), employment (3) and country's resilience (3).

Table 5: Overview of the pre-selected criteria and number of indicators for each criteria

Perspectives	Sub-objectives	No of indicators
A. ENVIRONMENTAL PERSPECTIVE		27
A.1	<u>Eco-friendly bioeconomy</u>	6
A.2	<u>Eco-friendly agriculture</u>	11
A.3	<u>Eco-friendly forestry</u>	7
A.4	<u>Eco-friendly aquaculture & fisheries</u>	3
B. SOCIAL PERSPECTIVE		11
B.1	<u>Bioeconomy acceptance/recognition</u>	5
B.2	<u>Fair and healthy society</u>	6
C. ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE		23
C.1	<u>Biomass availability</u>	5
C.2	<u>Competitiveness</u>	8
C.3	<u>Contribution to economic development</u>	4
C.4	<u>Employment</u>	3
C.5	<u>Country's resilience</u>	3
TOTAL		61

This set of pre-selected criteria and indicators was presented in the online survey (see description in the method section, chapter 2):

Environmental perspective

Tables 6 to 9 show the name, unit, and description of each indicator of the environmental perspective.

Table 6: Indicators of the environmental perspective – group A.1 Eco-friendly bioeconomy

A.1 <u>Eco-friendly bioeconomy</u>			
A.1.1	Fossil resources savings	kg Sb eq	Fossil resources saved by the production of bio-material replacing non-renewable resources; e.g. Wood-based constructions, bio-based textiles, bio-based furniture, bio-based plastics and bio-energy replacing non-renewable energy
A.1.2	Material Circularity for bio-based products	%	The circularity rate measures the share of material recycled and fed back into the economy in overall material use — thus reducing the extraction of primary raw materials.
A.1.3	Water resource savings	m ³ water eq	Water resources saved by the production of bio-material replacing non-renewable resources; e.g. Wood-based constructions, bio-based textiles, bio-based furniture, bio-based plastics and bio-energy replacing non-renewable energy
A.1.4	Greenhouse gas savings	kg CO ₂ eq	Greenhouse gas emissions saved by the production of bio-material replacing non-renewable resources; e.g. Wood-based constructions, bio-based textiles, bio-based furniture, bio-based plastics and bio-energy replacing non-renewable energy
A.1.5	Air quality: Particulate matter	deaths	This is an indicator that measures the potential risk of disease occurrence resulting from the emission of particulate matter. Particulate matter (PM) consists of solid particles and liquid droplets found in the air. PM can originate from various sources, typically arising from burning processes and activities that generate dust.
A.1.6	Material and waste recycling and recovery rate	%	Recycling/Recovery rates illustrate the proportion of waste that is recycled or recovered in comparison to the overall amount generated. Recycling encompasses material recycling, preparation for re-use, composting, and anaerobic digestion. Recovery pertains to waste from construction and demolition that is prepared for re-use, recycled, or subject to material recovery, including backfilling operations. These rates are reported for various waste types, such as municipal waste, packaging waste, and more.

Please note that indicator A.1.1 and A.1.4 are very similar but differ in the considered resources and emissions. A.1.1 “Fossil resources savings” is related to abiotic resource consumption (e.g. crude oil) and reflects the impact of avoided fossil fuels consumption. All resources are normalized to the characterization factor of antimony (Sb); therefore, the indicator is Sb equivalent (Sb eq). The indicator A.1.4 “Greenhouse gas savings” not only includes saved emissions from fossil fuel consumption but also any other greenhouse gas emissions from other origins (such as nitrous oxide that is produced in landfills, or methane that is produced at livestock farming). All emissions are normalized to the characterization factor of carbon dioxide (CO₂); therefore, the indicator is CO₂ equivalent (CO₂ eq).

Table 7: Indicators of the environmental perspective – group A.2 Eco-friendly agriculture

A.2 <u>Eco-friendly agriculture</u>			
A.2.1	Agricultural areas under Natura 2 000	hectare	The indicator gives information on the agricultural area which is covered by Natura 2000 habitats that depend on a continuation of extensive farming practices. The data and information for this factsheet provides data on area of habitat types dependent on agriculture under Natura 2000 areas (extensive agriculture, threatened by abandonment).
A.2.2	Area covered by protected habitat or species	hectare	The indicator gives information on the agricultural area which is covered by protected habitat or species classified under agri-environmental-climate interventions for protected areas in CAP 2023-2027
A.2.3	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	kgSOC per kg soil or %SOC	Carbon sequestration refers to the process of capturing and storing carbon emissions from the atmosphere using both physical and biological methods. A carbon stock, or carbon pool, is a system that has the capacity to store or release carbon. Examples for carbon stocks are soils, oceans or permafrost.
A.2.4	Climate resistant crops	%	climate resistant crops as percentage of total agricultural area
A.2.5	Nitrogen use	kg/ha	Nitrogen use for agricultural production
A.2.6	Phosphorus use	kg/ha	Phosphorus use for agricultural production
A.2.7	Rate of organic farming	%	Organic farming involves cultivating crops and raising animals without the use of synthetic farm inputs like fertilizers and pesticides. Instead, it relies on traditional methods such as green manure, compost manure, crop rotation, and other cultural practices to control pests and manage diseases.
A.2.8	Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture	%	Out of total agricultural area including marginal and abandoned land, the proportion of farming that contributes to protect the environment, efficient use the natural resources and to make the best use of nonrenewable resources
A.2.9	Soil condition	share of good soil quality out of all soil area in %	Soil condition refers to the ability of a particular soil to operate effectively within the confines of land use and ecosystem limitations. This involves supporting biological productivity, preserving environmental well-being, and fostering the health of plants, animals, and humans.
A.2.10	Food loss and waste reduction potential	%	Food loss and waste reduction leads to more efficient and low-waste food supply chain, saving resources, costs and emissions.
A.2.11	Agro-biodiversity	hectare; number of species	Number of livestock breeds; Number of crop varieties; Registered seeds for crops used for biomass production for industry; Number of threatened species in agricultural ecosystems, classified according to IUCN Red List categories in relation to total number of species in agricultural ecosystems Mean Species Abundance on agricultural lands

Table 8: Indicators of the environmental perspective – group A.3 Eco-friendly forestry

A.3 <u>Eco-friendly forestry</u>			
A.3.1	Climate change adaptation: Diversity of tree species	hectare; number of species	Area of forest and other wooded land, classified by number of tree species occurring
A.3.2	Deforestation	hectare	Deforestation refers to the decrease of forest area that are lost for other uses such as agricultural, croplands, urbanization, or mining activities.
A.3.3	Forest biodiversity	m ³ /ha; number of species	Volume of standing deadwood and of lying deadwood on forest and other wooded land (m ³ /ha); Number of threatened forest species, classified according to IUCN Red List categories in relation to total number of forest species.'
A.3.4	Forest fragmentation	%	loss of forest and the division of the remaining forest into smaller blocks Fragmentation amplifies the effects of the surrounding environment on the forest, especially at its edges.
A.3.5	Forest increments and fellings	%	Increments refer to the change in the size of a tree between the beginning and ending of a growth period. Fellings refer to the volume of all trees, which are felled during a given period, whether or not removed from the forest or other felling sites. Ratio of fellings and estimated maximum sustainable level of cuttings in forests.
A.3.6	Forests under management plan	%	A forest management plan defines the planned forestry activities (e.g. inventory, yield calculation, harvesting, silviculture, protection and monitoring), specifying objectives, actions and control arrangements in a forest area. A forest management plan is also an important tool for ensuring the participation of, and communicating forest objectives and strategies to, people living in or near the forest and other stakeholders in the implementation of SFM
A.3.7	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	kgSOC per kg soil or %SOC	Carbon sequestration refers to the process of capturing and storing carbon emissions from the atmosphere using both physical and biological methods. A carbon stock, or carbon pool, is a system that has the capacity to store or release carbon. Examples for carbon stocks are soils, oceans or permafrost.

Table 9: Indicators of the environmental perspective – group A.4 Eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries

A.4 <u>Eco-friendly aquaculture & fisheries</u>			
A.4.1	Aquatic biodiversity	number of species	Number of threatened species in water ecosystems, classified according to IUCN Red List categories in relation to total number of species in water ecosystems.
A.4.2	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	kgSOC per kg soil or %SOC	Carbon sequestration refers to the process of capturing and storing carbon emissions from the atmosphere using both physical and biological methods. A carbon stock, or carbon pool, is a system that has the capacity to store or release carbon. Examples for carbon stocks are soils, oceans or permafrost.
A.4.3	Marine protected area	km ²	A marine protected area is a defined region designated and managed for the long-term conservation of marine resources, ecosystems services, or cultural heritage.

Social perspective

Tables 10 to 11 show the name, unit, and description of each indicator of the social perspective.

Table 10: Indicators of the social perspective – group B.1 Bioeconomy acceptance/recognition

B.1 <u>Bioeconomy acceptance/recognition</u>			
B.1.1	Consumer awareness: consumer acceptance	qualitative	Consumer acceptance refers to the particular likes and dislikes of individual consumers when choosing products or services. This indicator might be measured by questionnaire (data collection from existing, public available information, or expert opinion)
B.1.2	Number of stakeholders from various stakeholder groups (i.e. public authorities, private business, NGOs, general public) involved in consultations	number of people	Gain key feedback on the various policy options under consideration, and in particular to gain insight into which policy option(s) is/are most likely to achieve the objectives set out in a manner that is cost-efficient and that imposes least burden. Measured in No. of people participating in consultations related to bioeconomy.
B.1.3	Education and knowledge: technical awareness	%	Knowledge capital is the value of an organization made up of its knowledge, relationships, learned techniques, procedures, and innovations. As a percentage of total employed person.
B.1.4	Participatory process: social acceptance	number of people	Individual biobased industry especially bioenergy projects regularly face resistance from the local community although social acceptance is influenced by stakeholder involvement both the awareness of climate change and its impacts, and the knowledge of the renewable energy technology. Measured in number of people participating in the meetings before the investments / number of investments.
B.1.5	Participatory process: involvement to decision making	number of opinions, number of investments	By involving stakeholders in the decision-making process, we create an opportunity to share ideas, learn from each other, device and work toward a common goal. The number of announcing opinions and suggestions can be measured and related to the number of investments

Table 11: Indicators of the social perspective – group B.2 Fair and healthy society

B.2 Fair and healthy society			
B.2.1	Household equality: Access to renewable energy	Share of total in %	Household access to a renewable energy (self-supply and net-supply).
B.2.2	Income equality : costs of a nutrition basket at city/community level	%	The indicator measures a medium cost of a diet meeting minimum requirements of macro- and micronutrients or food based dietary guidelines based on a weighted food price index. It can be measured by the share of the basket price to average salary.
B.2.3	Household equality: Access to separate waste collection	Share of total in %	The collection of individual components of solid waste from any source, usually separated into different collection containers, in order to recover, reuse or recycle the material or to facilitate its collection and disposal.
B.2.4	Regional equality: rural versus urban development	GDP/capita	Rural versus urban development: reducing poverty and unemployment by establishing basic social and economic infrastructure, training unemployed youth in rural areas, and providing jobs to marginal farmers and labourers in order to discourage seasonal and persistent migration to cities.
B.2.5	Gender equality	Share of total in %	Supply chain activities encompass a range of operations, including procurement, product lifecycle management, supply chain planning (which involves inventory planning, maintaining enterprise assets, and production lines), logistics (encompassing transportation and fleet management), and order management. The number of women engaged in these activities relative to the total number of employees is the share of women participating in supply chain activities.
B.2.6	Human Health	number of deaths	Measured with Human Toxicity Potential by means of LCA.

Economic perspective

Tables 12 to 16 show the name, unit, and description of each indicator of the economic perspective.

Table 12: Indicators of the economic perspective – group C.1 Biomass availability

C.1 <u>Biomass availability</u>			
C.1.1	Domestic biomass production in agriculture, forestry, aquaculture/fisheries	EUR/Mt; or kg/capita	Domestic production is related to products that are produced by companies located in the country and specifically targeted to the domestic population.
C.1.2	Biomass self-sufficiency rate in agriculture, forestry, aquatic	%	as the percentage of consumed products from agriculture, forestry and aquaculture that is produced in the country (Production x 100 / (Production + Imports–Exports))
C.1.3	Biomass net trade	%	Import and export of bioeconomy raw materials and products.
C.1.4	Production and consumption of non-food and feed bio-based products	monetary value	Non-food goods are consumer goods that are not edible (food items) and do not belong to the Fast Moving Consumer Goods (FMCG). Examples for this are clothing, electrical goods, etc. Bio-based products are either entirely or partially sourced from materials of biological origin, excluding those found in geological formations or that have fossilized over time.
C.1.5	Land cover: Agricultural area, forest area, aquacultural area	Share of total in %	Agricultural, forest and aquacultural area as a proportion of total land area.

Table 13: Indicators of the economic perspective – group C.2 Competitiveness

C.2 <u>Competitiveness</u>			
C.2.1	Advanced biorefinery technologies	number of patents	Biorefineries are classified based on, technological (implementation) status, type of raw materials used or main type of conversion processes applied. Conventional Biorefineries: 1st, 2nd, and 3rd Generation Biorefineries; Advanced Biorefineries: Lignocellulosic Feedstock Biorefineries
C.2.2	Number of firms in the (sub)sectors	Share of total in %	Number of firms in bioeconomy sectors as a proportion of total number of firms.
C.2.3	Private and public spending on research and development	EUR	R&D expenses are all costs associated with the research and development of your product or service, along with any intellectual property (IP) generated during the R&D phase, including patents and copyrights
C.2.4	Bio-based research and innovation activity	number of projects, funding sum	
C.2.5	Number of patents	number of national or international patents	A patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which is a product or a process that provides, in general, a new way of doing something, or offers a new technical solution to a problem. To get a patent, technical information about the invention must be disclosed to the public in a patent application
C.2.6	Certified bio-based products	Share of total in %	Number of bio-based products that are certified by acknowledged labelling schemes.
C.2.7	Market share of goods certified by independently verified sustainability labelling schemes	rate of change	Voluntary mark labelling consumer products as environment-friendly based on specific quality and environmental parameters
C.2.8	New products in biomass sectors	Share of total in %	Quantity and value of novel products.

Table 14: Indicators of the economic perspective – group C.3 Contribution to economic development

C.3 <u>Contribution to economic development</u>			
C.3.1	Terms-of-Trade of biomass	EUR per year and sub-sector	Ratio between the index of export prices and the index of import prices per biomass type
C.3.2	Turnover of bioeconomy sectors	Share of total in %	Turnover describes the level of business over a specific period of time, measured through the value of sales.
C.3.3	Contribution of bioeconomy sectors to GDP	Share of total in %	Gross domestic product (GDP) is the total value of all goods and services produced in a country.
C.3.4	Value added (bio-based sectors)	EUR	Value added represents the net production of a sector, obtained by adding all outputs and subtracting intermediate inputs. It's calculated without accounting for the decline of manufactured assets or the depletion and deterioration of natural resources. The bioeconomy, or biobased economy, uses renewable biological resources to produce food, energy and industrial goods.

Table 15: Indicators of the economic perspective – group C.4 Employment

C.4 <u>Employment</u>			
C.4.1	Employment in each group of bioeconomy subsectors	person-years	The number of people employed is the total number of persons who work in the observation unit, as well as persons who work outside the unit who belong to it (...) and are paid by it.
C.4.2	Job creation potential	FTE/output of bioeconomy sectors	Job creation means making new job openings, especially for people who didn't have work before or weren't in the job market. Job creation is measured through the number of full-time equivalent (FTE) jobs that were created. It aggregates part-time and full-time jobs.
C.4.3	Quality of employment	FTE/value added	Skilled labor usually involves more education and expertise gained through training and experience, often leading to higher pay. This is different from unskilled labor, which refers to people with a limited set of skills for work.

Table 16: Indicators of the economic perspective – group C.5 Country's resilience

C.5 <u>Country's resilience</u>			
C.5.1	Resilience to economic and social shocks/instability	points in a verbal scale	Resilience refers to a system's capability to sustain its operations despite unexpected disruptions. Economic shocks are unforeseen events that affect the economy, originating externally, such as the occurrence of unpredictable incidents like natural disasters or sudden changes in oil price.
C.5.2	Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption	Share of total in %	The renewable energy share in total final consumption is the percentage of final consumption of energy that is derived from renewable resources.
C.5.3	Import dependency ratio	%	Import dependency ratio refers to the extent of dependency on importation in relation to domestic consumption. For food items it can be measured by Grubel–Lloyd index.

5. Selected criteria and indicators by partners and stakeholders

This section presents the results of the survey.

General information of the participants in the survey

In total 70 out of 128 entries completed the survey (drop out rate: 45%). The majority of the participants were stakeholders (63%), so persons/organisations beyond the CEE2ACT consortium (see Figure 6). Most of the participants originate from Poland (20), followed by Greece (13), Slovakia (8), Serbia (7), Romania (7), Bulgaria (5), Netherlands (3), Czech Republic (3), Hungary (1) and Spain (1) (see also Figure 7).

CEE2ACT participants

Figure 6: Share of participants that are part of the CEE2ACT consortium

Number of participants by country
(n = 70)

Figure 7: Number of participants per country (n=70)

The sectors the participants were working in ranged from research and development (see Figure 8), to (39), to NGOs and voluntary groups and organisations (10), SMEs (8), Higher education (5), public service (6), state administration (1) and one large company.

Figure 8: Number of participants per sector (n=70)

The distribution by gender as shown in Figure 9 was nearly equal with 48% female and 46% male participants. 3% preferred not to say the gender and 3% defined their gender themselves.

Figure 9: Distribution by gender (n=70)

The sectors at which participants were working most were agriculture, food and feed, forestry and ecosystem services, while the rest ranged from 0 to 10% as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Distribution by bioeconomy sectors (multiple answers were possible)

Some participants indicated that they lack the knowledge to judge the level of measurability or the level of importance for specific indicators. The indicators with more than 9 such observations from participants are listed here (starting from the most observations):

- A.4.2 Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration (Level of measurability): 21
- C.3.1 Terms-of-Trade of biomass (Level of measurability): 19
- C.3.1 Terms-of-Trade of biomass (Level of importance): 18
- A.4.1 Aquatic biodiversity (Level of measurability): 16
- A.4.2 Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration (Level of importance): 15
- A.3.5 Forest increments and fellings (Level of measurability): 13
- A.3.7 Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration (Level of measurability): 13
- A.4.1 Aquatic biodiversity (Level of importance): 13
- A.2.5 Nitrogen use (Level of measurability): 12
- A.3.5 Forest increments and fellings (Level of importance): 12
- A.2.6 Human Health (Level of measurability): 11
- A.2.6 Human Health (Level of importance): 11
- A.4.3 Marine protected area (Level of measurability): 11
- A.4.3 Marine protected area (Level of importance): 11
- C.1.3 Biomass net trade (Level of measurability): 11

- A.2.3 Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration (Level of measurability): 10
- A.2.5 Nitrogen use (Level of importance): 10
- A.3.4 Forest fragmentation (Level of measurability): 10
- A.3.4 Forest fragmentation (Level of importance): 10
- A.3.6 Forests under management plan (Level of measurability): 10
- C.1.3 Biomass net trade (Level of importance): 10
- C.3.2 Turnover of bioeconomy sectors (Level of importance): 10
- C.5.1 Resilience to economic and social shocks/instability (Level of measurability): 10
- C.5.3 Import dependency ratio (Level of importance): 10

A.1 Eco-friendly bioeconomy

Indicators in the group A.1 eco-friendly bioeconomy were rated on average with 4.2 for their importance. The indicator with the highest rated level of importance is “material and waste recycling and recovery rate” (4.4). The rating on country level showed that participants from Slovakia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.9) and participants from Bulgaria, Spain, Hungary and Romania (average of 4.5).

Figure 11: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.1 Eco-friendly bioeconomy

Please note that the level of measurability was not asked for group A.1 eco-friendly bioeconomy because the indicators can be largely measured by means of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) which is foreseen as obligatory within this project. The measurability was automatically rated as high by researchers, as the individual indicators can be calculated using generic data.

A.2 Eco-friendly agriculture

Indicators in the group A.2 eco-friendly agriculture were rated on average with 3.9 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 12. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is “soil condition” (4.3). The rating on country level showed that participants from Slovenia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.5) and participants from Hungary as the highest (average of 4.8).

Figure 12: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.2 Eco-friendly agriculture

Indicators in the group A.2 eco-friendly agriculture were rated on average with 3.6 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 13. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Agricultural areas under Natura 2000” (4.2). The rating on country level showed that participants from Spain rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.6) and participants from Bulgaria and Romania the highest (average of 3.9).

Figure 13: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.2 Eco-friendly agriculture

A.3 Eco-friendly forestry

Indicators in the group A.3 eco-friendly forestry were rated on average with 4.1 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 14. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is “Deforestation” with 4.4. The rating on country level showed that participants from Slovenia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.1) and participants from Hungary the highest (average of 5.0).

Figure 14: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.3 Eco-friendly forestry

Indicators in the group A.3 eco-friendly forestry were rated on average with 3.7 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 15. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is again “Deforestation” with 4.3. The rating on country level showed that participants from Spain rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.6) and participants from Bulgaria the highest (average of 4.4).

Figure 15: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.3 Eco-friendly forestry

A.4 Eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries

Indicators in the group A.4 eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries were rated on average with 3.8 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 16. The indicators with the highest average levels of importance are “Aquatic biodiversity” and “Change in carbon stocks/carbon sequestration” with 4.9 each. The rating on country level showed that participants from Slovenia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.2) and participants from Hungary the highest (average of 5).

Figure 16: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.4 Eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries

Indicators in the group A.4 eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries were rated on average with 3.6 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 17. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Marine protected area” with an average of 4.1. The rating on country level showed that participants from Spain rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.0) and participants from Bulgaria the highest (average of 4.2).

Figure 17: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group A.4 Eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries

A.0 Additional environmental indicators

Nine participants added additional indicators for the environmental perspective. They are listed below. Please note that some participants mentioned the indicator name and some rather a description of the indicator. Additional environmental indicators, units or aspects mentioned by participants of the survey are:

- (1) carbon emissions of each bioeconomy activity / sector (except for carbon sequestration in some of the sectors) (measurability: 5, importance: 4)
- (2) air, water, soil pollution (measurability: 5, importance: 4)
- (3) Life Cycle Assessment integrated with Circular Economy (measurability: 5, importance: 4)
- (4) Carbon Mean Residence Time - e.g. for SOC stock. Unquestionably, not all carbon compounds are equally durable with some degrading faster than others (e.g. fresh plant residue degrades rapidly, while older "humic" substance or charcoal are fairly recalcitrant). Thus, overall "sequestration value" of a given carbon stock is related not only to the amount of carbon stored, but also to its longevity. Hence Mean Residence Time metric should be summoned in order to provide for a more comprehensive value judgement. (measurability: 4, importance: 5)
- (5) Financial incentive measures for actors of environmental protection (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (6) Punitive financial measures for actors who disturb the ecological balance and influence the degradation of the environment (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (7) Innovate curricula and programs at all levels of education aimed at preserving, protecting and improving the environment (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (8) Use of Res sources in energy mixt (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (9) Land use (%ha), fragmentation of land urban/rural, land use for biomass and bioeconomy purposes (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (10) Ecosystem services and biodiversity (measurability: 4, importance: 5)
- (11) # of worms per unit of soil (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (12) Ecological Urbanized territories - urban and suburban parks and gardens, roadside rows and small groups of trees - with indicators such as e.g. %/ ha coverage of the urban environment; species diversity (and/or tree age); attendance - number of inhabitants/weekly or daily; health status - % of trees damaged on average / in need of replacement (measurability: 5, importance: 4)
- (13) VCS - Verified Carbon Standard Program / Verra's Verified Carbon Standards Program, to make better use of existing carbon credit programs. Such a /similar/ indicator would stimulate economic entities to look for certified productions that are convertible on the

stock market. This would stimulate all producers to produce more ecologically, and when this is impossible - to look for compensatory "green certificates" to buy back their carbon-emitting production. (measurability: 3, importance: 5)

B.1 Bioeconomy acceptance/recognition

Indicators in the group B.1 bioeconomy acceptance and recognition were rated on average with 4.1 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 18. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is "Consumer awareness: consumer acceptance" with an average of 4.3. The rating on country level showed that participants from the Netherlands, Poland and Slovenia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.7) and participants from Hungary the highest (average of 5.0).

Figure 18: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group B.1 bioeconomy acceptance and recognition

Indicators in the group B.1 bioeconomy acceptance and recognition were rated on average with 3.3 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 19. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Number of stakeholders from various stakeholder groups” with an average of 3.8. The rating on country level showed that participants from Hungary rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.6) and participants from Spain the highest (average of 4.3).

Group B.1: Bioeconomy acceptance/recognition

Figure 19: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group B.1 bioeconomy acceptance and recognition

B.2 Fair and healthy society

Indicators in the group B.2 fair and healthy society were rated on average with 3.7 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 20. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is “Human health” with an average of 4.0. The rating on country level showed that participants from Hungary rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.6) and participants from Slovenia the highest (average of 4.3).

Figure 20: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group B.2 Fair and healthy society

Indicators in the group B.2 fair and healthy society were rated on average with 3.8 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 21. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Household equality: access to separate waste collection” with an average of 4.2. The rating on country level showed that participants from Slovenia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.8) and participants from Spain the highest (average of 4.6).

Figure 21: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group B.2 Fair and healthy society

B.0 Additional social indicators

Three participants suggested additional social indicators:

- (1) Digital equality (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (2) Household access to subsidy for bioenergy source-housing renovation (measurability: 4, importance: 4)
- (3) Standard of citizens and ability to pay (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (4) Culture of living and housing (measurability: 5, importance: 5)
- (5) Political and economic stability in the country (measurability: 5, importance: 5)

C.1 Biomass availability

Indicators in the group C.1 biomass availability were rated on average with 4.1 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 22. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is “Domestic biomass production in agriculture, forestry, aquaculture/fisheries” with an average of 4.3. The rating on country level showed that participants from Poland rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.7) and participants from Hungary the highest (average of 5.0).

Figure 22: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.1 Biomass availability

Indicators in the group C.1 biomass availability were rated on average with 3.8 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 23. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Land cover: Agricultural area, forest area, aquacultural area” with an average of 4.6. The rating on country level showed that participants from Greece, Poland and Serbia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.6) and participants from Slovenia the highest (average of 4.8).

Figure 23: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.1 Biomass availability

C.2 Competitiveness

Indicators in the group C.2 competitiveness were rated on average with 3.9 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 24. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is “Private and public spending on research and development” with an average of 4.2. The rating on country level showed that participants from the Netherlands rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.2) and participants from Hungary the highest (average of 5.0).

Figure 24: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.2 Competitiveness

Indicators in the group C.2 competitiveness were rated on average with 3.8 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 25. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Number of patents” with an average of 4.2. The rating on country level showed that participants from Serbia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.6) and participants from Hungary as the highest (average of 4.6).

Figure 25: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.2 Competitiveness

C.3 Contribution to economic development

Indicators in the group C.3 contribution to economic development were rated on average with 4.2 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 26. The indicators with the highest average level of importance are “Contribution of bioeconomy sectors to GDP” and “Value added (bio-based sectors)” with an average of 4.4 each. The rating on country level showed that participants from Netherlands and Poland rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.8 each) and participants from Hungary and Spain as the highest (average of 5.0 each).

Figure 26: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.3 Contribution to economic development

Indicators in the group C.3 contribution to economic development were rated on average with 3.5 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 26. The indicators with the highest average level of measurability are “Turnover of bioeconomy sectors” and “Contribution of bioeconomy sectors to GDP” with an average of 3.7 each. The rating on country level showed that participants from Serbia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.8) and participants from Bulgaria as the highest (average of 4.1).

Figure 27: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.3 Contribution to economic development

C.4 Employment

Indicators in the group C.4 employment were rated on average with 4.1 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 28. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is “Job creation potential” with an average of 4.2. The rating on country level showed that participants from the Netherlands rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.1) and participants from Hungary as the highest (average of 5.0).

Figure 28: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.4 Employment

Indicators in the group C.4 employment were rated on average with 3.3 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 29. The indicator with the highest average level of measurability is “Employment in each group of bioeconomy subsectors” with an average of 3.8. The rating on country level showed that participants from the Netherlands rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 2.6) and participants from Romania as the highest (average of 3.7).

Figure 29: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.4 Employment

C.5 Country's resilience

Indicators in the group C.5 country's resilience were rated on average with 4.2 for their importance. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 30. The indicator with the highest average level of importance is "Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption" with an average of 4.5. The rating on country level showed that participants from Slovakia rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.8) and participants from Hungary as the highest (average of 5.0).

Figure 30: Average level of importance across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.5 Country's resilience

Indicators in the group C.5 country's resilience were rated on average with 3.5 for their measurability. The average values in total and for each country are shown in Figure 31. The indicators with the highest average level of measurability are "Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption" and "Import dependency ratio" with an average of 4.0 each. The rating on country level showed that participants from Spain

rated the indicators in this group the lowest (average of 3.0) and participants from Slovenia as the highest (average of 4.0).

Figure 31: Average level of measurability across all participants (plot) and by country (table) – Group C.5 Country's resilience

C.0 Additional economic indicators

One participant had another suggestion for an economic indicator:

- (1) The stability of the domestic currency, financially stimulate and promote investment programs for the preservation and protection of the environment (measurability: 5, importance: 5)

6. Set of criteria

The level of importance was defined as a key criterion for the selection of indicators. As a second step the level of measurability is another criterion, because even if the indicator is defined as important it is possible that it is not likely to be measurable. In a data-driven approach that we have foreseen in the project, it is crucial to select indicators that are suitable to both: importance and measurability. The average across all participants for each indicator is shown in the annex.

Table 17: Set of indicators above the average level of importance

ID	Indicator name	Importance >4	Measurability
A.1.1	Fossil resources savings	4.2	5
A.1.2	Material Circularity for bio-based products	4.3	5
A.1.3	Water resource savings	4.4	5
A.1.4	Greenhouse gas savings	4.2	5
A.1.6	Material and waste recycling and recovery rate	4.4	5
A.2.3	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	4.2	3.3
A.2.9	Soil condition	4.3	3.6
A.2.10	Food loss and waste reduction potential	4.2	3.3
A.3.1	Climate change adaptation: Diversity of tree species	4.0	3.7
A.3.2	Deforestation	4.4	4.3
A.3.3	Forest biodiversity	4.0	3.7
A.3.6	Forests under management plan	4.1	4.1
A.3.7	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	4.3	3.2
B.1.1	Consumer awareness: consumer acceptance	4.3	3.1
B.1.3	Education and knowledge: technical awareness	4.1	3.1
B.1.5	Participatory process: involvement to decision making	4.1	3.4
B.2.3	Household equality: Access to separate waste collection	4.2	3.7
C.1.1	Domestic biomass production in agriculture, forestry, aquaculture/fisheries	4.3	3.9
C.1.4	Production and consumption of non-food and feed bio-based products	4.0	3.5
C.1.5	Land cover: Agric. area, forest area, aquacultural area	4.1	4.6
C.2.3	Private and public spending on research and develop.	4.2	4.0
C.2.4	Bio-based research and innovation activity	4.1	4.0
C.3.2	Turnover of bioeconomy sectors	4.2	3.7
C.3.3	Contribution of bioeconomy sectors to GDP	4.4	3.7
C.3.4	Value added (bio-based sectors)	4.4	3.4
C.4.2	Job creation potential	4.2	3.2
C.5.2	Renewable energy share in total final energy consumption	4.5	4.0
C.5.3	Import dependency ratio	4.1	4.0

The average across all indicators is 4 regarding the level of importance. All indicators above this average level are listed in Table 17 below. This selection process reduced the number of indicators from 61 to 28 indicators that are most important.

When considering the list of indicators in Table 17, all sections are covered except for eco-friendly aquaculture and fisheries. A further selection regarding the level of measurability is foreseen in the next step of the project. This deliverable though presents a thorough basis for future decisions, which might be still expanded if required.

7. References

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8. Annex

List of indicators from articles

Criteria	Indicator	Unit	Sub-objectives based on sustainability concept	Sub-objective based on EU bioeconomy strategy objectives
APPROPRIATE RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT, MONITORING AND ACCOUNTABILITY SYSTEMS ARE PUT IN PLACE AND IMPLEMENTED	EMAS eco-management		Economic criteria	Climate change
CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF BIOECONOMY GOODS MATCH SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY LEVELS OF BIOMASS	SDG 8.4.1/12.2.1 Material footprint , material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP	?	Economic criteria	Climate change
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption	%	Economic criteria	Climate change
Bio-based sectors fossil substitution	# employees	#	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	As a measure of green technology innovation, patent publication in environmental technology by filing office	% of total patents	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Average income of employees in the bioeconomy sectors	\$	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Change in turnover of bio-based sectors	%	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
LOCAL ECONOMIES ARE NOT BE HAMPERED BUT RATHER HARNESSSED BY THE TRADE OF RAW AND PROCESSED BIOMASS, AND RELATED TECHNOLOGIES	Change in wood net trade	%	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Cluster size (number of businesses or employees in each cluster)	% of total firms	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	Commercialization of innovative technologies	sales of innovation products	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
To assess biomass flows within the EU between the rest of the world (Employment and economic competitiveness)	Comparative advantage		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
DEMAND AND SUPPLY- SIDE MARKET MECHANISMS AND POLICY COHERENCE BETWEEN SUPPLY AND DEMAND OF FOOD AND NONFOOD GOODS ARE ENHANCED	Consumer preferences (consumer demand)	?	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Contribution of bioeconomy sectors to GDP	%	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Contribution of forest sector to GDP	%	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Cost-competitiveness of biofuels compared with non-renewable energy sources		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
COOPERATION, COLLABORATION AND SHARING OF RESOURCES, SKILLS AND TECHNOLOGIES ARE ENHANCED WHEN AND WHERE APPROPRIATE	Density of firms in the (sub)sectors	?	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Development of advanced biorefinery technologies for the production of energy and materials	?	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
EXISTING KNOWLEDGE IS ADEQUATELY VALUED AND PROVEN SOUND TECHNOLOGIES ARE FOSTERED	Diffusion of technology	?	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Domestic and foreign investments into bioeconomy sectors	\$	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Income generation	Employment (# benefited annually)		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Employment in each group of bioeconomy subsectors	% of total employment	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Employment multiplier		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	<p>Employment status/decent jobs/income generated for small farmers</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • -Number of persons employed at various stages of bio product supply chain. • -Average number of days /hours people work per year in the full value chain in bioeconomy. • -Number of jobs created in the full value chain in the bioeconomy. • -Minimum wages earned for workers in bioeconomy sectors. • Number of enterprises registered in the bioeconomy sector • Proportion provided with training/ education to do the job 	<p>Economic criteria</p>	<p>Competitiveness and creating jobs</p>
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LOCAL ECONOMIES ARE NOT BE HAMPERED BUT RATHER HARNESSSED BY THE TRADE OF RAW AND PROCESSED BIOMASS, AND RELATED TECHNOLOGIES	Export and import of biomass related technologies (see 10.1)		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
LOCAL ECONOMIES ARE NOT BE HAMPERED BUT RATHER HARNESSSED BY THE TRADE OF RAW AND PROCESSED BIOMASS, AND RELATED TECHNOLOGIES	Export of environmental goods according to OECD and APEC	% of total export	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Exports		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Forest holdings		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Full direct jobs equivalent in the biomass consuming region (or country)		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Full Time Equivalent jobs		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

Income distribution	Gini index		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Income generation	Gross average income		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Gross fixed capital formation in relation to GDP		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Bio-based sectors fossil substitution	Gross value added		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Growth of specific bio-based technologies, processes or products		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Household income	\$	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

To assess biomass flows within the EU between the rest of the world (Employment and economic competitiveness)	Import of bioeconomy raw materials and products		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Inclusive Wealth Index	millions of constant US\$/capita	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Income	(95% of people earning above \$1.90 a day)	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Income creation	value of jobs created within bioeconomy sector	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

Income distribution	Income distribution along the chain		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Bioresource sectors	Income multipliers		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Innovation – new products in total FWC and by subsector		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	Intellectual property rights (IPRs) (patent, trademark, design) applications in bioeconomy subsectors	number of application per 1 000 employees	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	Investment in R&D	\$	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	<p>Investments in research and development / technology</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage use of new technologies/ innovation skills in bioeconomy. • Percentage of sectors/industries utilizing newer technologies in the production of bioeconomy goods and services. • Percentage of groups with access to research materials and outcomes. • Percentage of people accessing training and extension services. 	<p>Economic criteria</p>	<p>Competitiveness and creating jobs</p>
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INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Job creation in skilled / unskilled labour		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	Key enabling technology (KET) R&D focus	?	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Apparent labour productivity of the bioeconomy	Labour productivity	EUR of VA / person employed in each sector	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Location quotient	proportion of persons employed in a particular sector and in a given Member State compared with the European proportion	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

Commercialization	Market share		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Net energy balance		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	<p>Net energy balance / Access to Modern Energy and energy security</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Percentage use of new technologies/ innovation skills in bioeconomy. • Percentage of sectors/industries utilizing newer technologies in the production of bioeconomy goods and services. • Percentage of groups with access to research materials and outcomes. • Percentage of people accessing training and extension services. 	<p>Economic criteria</p>	<p>Competitiveness and creating jobs</p>
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INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	Number of employed persons in rural and urban areas	1 000 persons	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
APPROPRIATE RISK ASSESSMENT AND MANAGEMENT, MONITORING AND ACCOUNTABILITY SYSTEMS ARE PUT IN PLACE AND IMPLEMENTED	Number of spatial conflicts (between current / future human activities and nature)		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Income generation	Other sources of income		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Commercialization	Participation in institutional programs		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Primary and high tech sectors	Patents		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	Productivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ratio of productivity efficiency (high or low). • Volume of bioproducts generated per year. • Life-cycle costs; the minimum costs of production in manufacturing bio resources such as biofuels 	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	Prominent universities or research institute	quality of university	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
RESILIENCE OF THE RURAL AND URBAN ECONOMY IS ENHANCED	Proximity to financial institutions	distance to closest major financial centre	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

DEMAND AND SUPPLY- SIDE MARKET MECHANISMS AND POLICY COHERENCE BETWEEN SUPPLY AND DEMAND OF FOOD AND NONFOOD GOODS ARE ENHANCED	Public financial support and private investments for ecosystem services	\$	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	Quality of workforce (secondary and tertiary education)	(% of total population)	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	R&D employment	% of total employment	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Resilience to economic and social shocks/instability	?	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	SEIB (SEIB is a dimensionless indicator derived from the interaction between three variables: i) the value of the socio-economic parameters for each sector (VP), ii) the weight of the socio-economic parameters for each sector (WP) and iii) the weight of the bio-based sectors (WS))		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Share of biofuel industry that is part of the bioeconomy in terms of GDP, employment, turnover		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Share of chemical industry that is part of the bioeconomy in terms of GDP, employment, turnover		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
KNOWLEDGE GENERATION AND INNOVATION ARE PROMOTED	SME birth rate	% of total firms	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	Specific number of unemployed of wood yield of felling age per 1 ha against number of wood processing and wood product manufacturing businesses	Number of unemployed /m3 /ha / Number of businesses	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Specific number of wood processing and wood product manufacturing businesses per wood yield of felling age per 1 ha] against 1 ha of total wood yield of felling age	Number of businesses/m3 /ha / m3	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Total Net Profit (TNP)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Value of net profit generated from conversion /processing of main products and byproducts 	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	Total value added	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sum of value added generated from biomass development process, i.e. in all production processes of main products and byproducts. • Value of GDP per capita • Value added at local level 	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Trade in wood		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
RESILIENCE OF THE RURAL AND URBAN ECONOMY IS ENHANCED	Transport of freight (proxy)	tonnes per km ²	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
The concentration of national labour markets into the bioeconomy	Turnover	EUR	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IS FOSTERED	Turnover/output of bioeconomy sectors	\$	Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Turnover/Workers		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Use and development of biotechnology in the bioeconomy		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
To assess product uptake of bio-based production (Employment and economic competitiveness)	Value Added of the bioeconomy sectors		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
	Value Added/Workers		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Ensuring food security	Value and quantity of marketed non-wood goods from forest and other wooded land		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Managing natural resources sustainably	Value of marketed services on forest and other wooded land		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Wood energy		Economic criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Food security and nutrition are supported	Agricultural factor income per annual work (AWU)	Index	Economic criteria	Food security
DEMAND AND SUPPLY- SIDE MARKET MECHANISMS AND POLICY COHERENCE BETWEEN SUPPLY AND DEMAND OF FOOD AND NONFOOD GOODS ARE ENHANCED	Change in food prices (see 1.1.a); real wood prices; forest products prices		Economic criteria	Food security
DEMAND AND SUPPLY- SIDE MARKET MECHANISMS AND POLICY COHERENCE BETWEEN SUPPLY AND DEMAND OF FOOD AND NONFOOD GOODS ARE ENHANCED	Current levelised life-cycle cost, and future levelised life-cycle costs of biomass		Economic criteria	Food security

Food security and nutrition are supported	Food purchasing power	percent	Economic criteria	Food security
DEMAND AND SUPPLY- SIDE MARKET MECHANISMS AND POLICY COHERENCE BETWEEN SUPPLY AND DEMAND OF FOOD AND NONFOOD GOODS ARE ENHANCED	Food, fuelwood and other products supply security (Measures to avoid risks for negative impacts on price and supply of national food basket, fuelwood and other products.)		Economic criteria	Food security
Food security and nutrition are supported	New food products (by sector)		Economic criteria	Food security
Food security and nutrition are supported	New food value chains (by sector)		Economic criteria	Food security
Managing natural resources sustainably	Age structure and/or diameter distribution		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
To assess independence from biomass imports (Sustainable natural resource management)	Biomass self-sufficiency rate		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Cascading use of biomass		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
SUSTAINABLE INTENSIFICATION OF BIOMASS PRODUCTION IS PROMOTED	Domestic production of agricultural, blue, forestry and waste biomass (kg/capita)	kg / capita	Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability

Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Economic impacts of invasive species		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Genetically modified trees		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Illegal logging and associated trade		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Increment and fellings		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
DEMAND AND SUPPLY- SIDE MARKET MECHANISMS AND POLICY COHERENCE BETWEEN SUPPLY AND DEMAND OF FOOD AND NONFOOD GOODS ARE ENHANCED	Market share of goods certified by independently verified sustainability labelling schemes		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
To assess the degree of circularity (Sustainable natural resource management)	Material use efficiency		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Natural resource index		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
To assess biomass availability (Sustainable natural resource management)	Primary Biomass production		Economic criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Ammonia, NOx and SOx emissions	ktonnes	Environmental criteria	Climate change
Reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	Carbon footprint		Environmental criteria	Climate change
CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	CO ₂ eq. Tonnes	Environmental criteria	Climate change
RESILIENCE OF BIOMASS PRODUCERS, RURAL COMMUNITIES AND ECOSYSTEMS IS DEVELOPED AND/OR STRENGTHENED	Change in ecosystem service provision		Environmental criteria	Climate change

CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	Change in GHG emissions	CO ₂ eq	Environmental criteria	Climate change
CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	Change in LULUCF carbon baseline		Environmental criteria	Climate change
CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	CO ₂ emissions (2°C warming)		Environmental criteria	Climate change
SUSTAINABLE INTENSIFICATION OF BIOMASS PRODUCTION IS PROMOTED	Ecological Footprint	(global hectares/capita/year)	Environmental criteria	Climate change
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Emissions of non-GHG air pollutants, including air toxics, from: (1) feedstock production (mg/ha, mg/MJ, and as a percentage), (2) processing (mg/m ³ or ppm), (3) transport of feedstocks, intermediate products and end products	mg/MJ	Environmental criteria	Climate change
RESILIENCE OF BIOMASS PRODUCERS, RURAL COMMUNITIES AND ECOSYSTEMS IS DEVELOPED AND/OR STRENGTHENED	Eutrophication of ecosystems		Environmental criteria	Climate change
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Level of emission of air pollutants (PM _{2.5} , PM ₁₀ , SO ₂ eq)		Environmental criteria	Climate change

THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Life cycle emissions of SO ₂ , NO _x , NH ₃ and HCl/HF from bioenergy provision, expressed in SO ₂ equivalents and calculated in accordance to GHG emission		Environmental criteria	Climate change
CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	Life cycle-based CO ₂ eq including direct land use change, and other GHG emission	gCO ₂ eq/MJ	Environmental criteria	Climate change
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Presence of water pollutants (e.g. nitrate, phosphorous, pesticides, biochemical oxygen demand)		Environmental criteria	Climate change
CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	Public financial support and private investments for mitigation and adaptation	\$	Environmental criteria	Climate change
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	SDG 11.6.2 Annual mean levels of fine particulate matter (e.g. PM _{2.5} and PM ₁₀) in cities	population weighted	Environmental criteria	Climate change
CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	SDG 13.2.1 Number of countries that have communicated the establishment or operationalization of an integrated policy/strategy/plan which increases their ability to adapt to the adverse impacts of climate change, and foster climate resilience and low greenhouse gas emissions development in a manner that does not threaten food production (including a national adaptation plan, nationally determined contribution, national communication, biennial update report or other)		Environmental criteria	Climate change
RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, WASTE PREVENTION AND WASTE RE-USE ALONG THE WHOLE BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAIN IS IMPROVED	SDG 8.4.1/12.2.1 Material footprint, material footprint per capita, and material footprint per GDP		Environmental criteria	Climate change

CLIMATE CHANGE MITIGATION AND ADAPTATION ARE PURSUED	SDG 9.4.1 CO2 emission per unit of value added		Environmental criteria	Climate change
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Average marine acidity (pH) measured at agreed suite of representative sampling stations (SDG 14.3.1)		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Indispensable to assess the impact of biomass production at the genetic, species, and ecosystem level (Sustainable natural resource management)	Biodiversity		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
To assess the direct substitutability of fossil resources with biological resources (Sustainable natural resource management)	Bio-energy replacing non-renewable energy (Dependence on non-renewable resources)		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
To assess the direct substitutability of fossil resources with biological resources (Sustainable natural resource management)	Bio-material replacing non-renewable resources		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Ensuring food security	Blue water footprint		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
To assess the variety of products from bio-based production (Sustainable natural resource management)	Certified bio-based products		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Deadwood		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Defoliation		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability

Waste recovery	Degree of waste recovery by product		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Deposition and concentration of air pollutants on forest and other wooded land		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Bio-based sectors fossil substitution	Energy consumption		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, WASTE PREVENTION AND WASTE RE-USE ALONG THE WHOLE BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAIN IS IMPROVED	Energy intensity of the economy		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, WASTE PREVENTION AND WASTE RE-USE ALONG THE WHOLE BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAIN IS IMPROVED	Energy use (kg of oil equivalent) per USD 1 000 GDP (constant 2011 PPP)	kg of oil equivalent per USD 1000 GDP	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
RESILIENCE OF BIOMASS PRODUCERS, RURAL COMMUNITIES AND ECOSYSTEMS IS DEVELOPED AND/OR STRENGTHENED	Environmental protection: 1. Protected forest areas (1 000 ha); 2. Standing and lying dead wood in forests (m ³ /ha); 3. Agricultural areas under Natura 2 000 (ha); 4. Area under agri-environmental commitments (ha); 5. Number of threatened species	ha ; m ³ /ha ; ha ; ha	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Eutrophication (N,P concentration)	N, P concentration	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability

THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Fish resources	tonnes	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Forest area		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Forest area density	% of total land	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Mitigating and adapting to climate change	Forest damage		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
	Forest footprint		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Forest fragmentation		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Forests under management plan		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Bio-based sectors fossil substitution	Fossil resources savings		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Freshwater resources	billion m ³	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Growing stock on forests available for wood supply	1000 m ³	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE	Maritime space assigned for [Blue Economy sector X]		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability

ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED				
RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, WASTE PREVENTION AND WASTE RE-USE ALONG THE WHOLE BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAIN IS IMPROVED	Material and waste recycling and recovery rate	toe	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF BIOECONOMY GOODS MATCH SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY LEVELS OF BIOMASS	Net energy balance (Energy ratio of the bioenergy value chain with comparison with other energy sources, including energy ratios of: (1) feedstock production; (2) processing of feedstock into bioenergy; (3) bioenergy use; and/or (4) lifecycle analysis.)		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Nitrate in groundwater		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
RESILIENCE OF BIOMASS PRODUCERS, RURAL COMMUNITIES AND ECOSYSTEMS IS DEVELOPED AND/OR STRENGTHENED	Non indigenous species		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
RESOURCE EFFICIENCY, WASTE PREVENTION AND WASTE RE-USE ALONG THE WHOLE BIOECONOMY VALUE CHAIN IS IMPROVED	Organic waste diverted from landfills		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Percentage of land for which soil quality (SOC) is maintained or improved out of total land on which bioeconomy feedstock is cultivated or harvested	%	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
Managing natural resources sustainably	Protected forests		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
CONSUMPTION PATTERNS OF BIOECONOMY GOODS MATCH SUSTAINABLE SUPPLY LEVELS OF BIOMASS	Public financial support and private investments for reducing dependence on non-renewable resources	\$	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability

THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Ratio of annual increment and fellings in forest	%	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Ratio of fellings and estimated maximum sustainable level of cuttings in forestst	%	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Soil erosion	tonnes/ha	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Total phosphate in flowing wate		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Water use efficiency (Water use for biomass production (cropping), irrigation, and processing/kg biomass)	processing/kg biomass	Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
WATER QUALITY AND QUANTITY ARE MAINTAINED, AND, IN AS MUCH AS POSSIBLE, ENHANCED	Water use for agriculture and forestry		Environmental criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability
	Fossil-resource saving		Environmental criteria	Non-renewable resources
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Index of coastal eutrophication (ICEP) and floating plastic debris density (SDG 14.1.1)		Environmental criteria	Non-renewable resources

THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Nitrogen balance	kg/ha	Environmental criteria	Non-renewable resources
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Pesticides sales	tonnes	Environmental criteria	Non-renewable resources
THE DEGRADATION OF LAND, SOIL, FORESTS AND MARINE ENVIRONMENTS IS PREVENTED, STOPPED OR REVERSED	Phosphorus balance	kg/ha	Environmental criteria	Non-renewable resources
Community participation in decision making	% of women participating in supply chain activities		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
To assess policies, strategies, and legislation on the bioeconomy (Employment and economic competitiveness)	Bioeconomy-driving Policies		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

	Education and knowledge capital	literacy rates Average schooling Information access Percentage of employees participating in training per total employees	Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Education time in total FWC and training expenditure as % of turnover in total FWC		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Traditional indicator applied in more sectorial and spatial detail (Employment and economic competitiveness)	Employment		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH IS STRENGTHENED	GINI index (measure of inequality of income or wealth)	70 on 0-100 scale (Gini index of 0.30)	Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs

Education and training of human resources	HDI education		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Bio-based sectors fossil substitution	Patents		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Increasing competitiveness and creating jobs	Production and employment in woodworking, manufacture of pulp, paper and paper-board, converting, printing		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Bio-based sectors fossil substitution	Publications		Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
EXISTING KNOWLEDGE IS ADEQUATELY VALUED AND PROVEN SOUND TECHNOLOGIES ARE FOSTERED	Training and re-qualification of the workforce in the bioeconomy sector	share of workers, % per year	Social criteria	Competitiveness and creating jobs
Nutrition	Nutrition (threshold of 2 700 kcal per capita	kcal / per capita	Social criteria	Food security
FOOD SAFETY, DISEASE PREVENTION AND HUMAN HEALTH ARE ENSURED	Organic farming		Social criteria	Food security
Managing natural resources sustainably	Urban forestry and human health		Social criteria	Natural Resources and sustainability

Indicators from POWER4BIO

1. Availability and use of resources: this criteria relates to the availability and access to raw materials, trends in demand, evolution, information and statistics on available types of feedstock, as well as their existing and potential competitors for its use.	
Production efficiency of agricultural/forestry/fish-ery/aquaculture/other production in the region (average production yield/year)	currently; potential scenario by 2030
Current exploitation of waste and residues streams in the region	currently; potential scenario by 2030
Region existent resources' characteristics (physical and chemical)	
Constraints leading to low production yields (for example low water availability in the region)	
Raw material supply and demand balance at re-gional, national and international scale	Imported biomass and/or resi-dues; Exported biomass and/or resi-dues
Long-term competitive and consistent availability of the resources at regional level	currently; potential scenario by 2030
Existence of multiple consumers for the feedstock (competition over the resource)	
Potential for higher valorisation of resources	
2. Infrastructure/Industrial factors: intends to draw a picture of the set of infrastructures and installations that enable the link between feedstock production sites, collection nodes, production and consumption, to meet the requirements of the supply chains, considering that these aspects are key decision factors for investors. Infrastructure and technologies for the treatment and utilization of the feedstock are considered.	

Existence and level of development of agro-food, fishery, livestock, aquaculture, wood/paper value chains or waste recovery infrastructure with a strong technological specialisation in the region (logistic for the existent feedstocks in the region)	
Existence of necessary infrastructure to host bio-based solutions in the region	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Availability of logistic services (significant number of logistic operator); o Homogeneous distribution within the region/ surrounding regions of these logistical services; o Existence of areas with concentration of services and industry (industrial parks)
Type and size of the existing industries, farm exploitations, etc. in the region adequate for the implementation of bio-based value chain	
Active presence of actors required along the value chain in the region or on the contrary lack of any of the actors required along the bio-based value chain	
3. Research and innovation: is related to the supporting institutions such as universities, testing and certification bodies, research institutions, and other organizations that could build and transfer know-how and offer technical and technological assistance to the entrepreneurship willing to be or already being part of the Regional Bioeconomy Strategy.	
Establishment of scientific network with researchers and industry stakeholders to increase the capacity of the region/country on fields related to bioeconomy	
Existence of technological expertise in technology transfer process	

Development of pilot scale plants producing of bio-based products (for instance as part of research projects)	
Knowledge on bioeconomy related topics available for the public (existence of information compiled that would allow to solve doubts regarding the value chain, cost, funding available, sustainability, etc.)	
Existence of operational industrial and research clusters (size, management and governance) or en-tities communicating coherent and reliable data	
Number of patents related to bioeconomy field registered in the region and country	
Development of training programmes and performance of learning activities, mostly related to the emerging technology, but also related to markets, networks, users etc.	
Correlation between industrial needs and research activities (research activities provide support re-garding emerging technology to industrial actors)	
Existence of coaching programs to identify oppor-tunities and assist companies interested (coaching services)	
4. Market/Economic aspects: focus on the framework conditions for establishing regional markets, including: production conditions of biobased products, potential clients of regional production, innovative producers, institutions facilitating networking, investment framework, etc.	

Active local and global markets and easy access for bio-based products	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Difficulties for companies to access local and global market; Difficulties to launch a new bio-based product; o Actions carried out to create a demand for the emerging technology/product
Production costs of bio-based products comparing to alternative non bio-based products	
Competitive advantages of the bio-based product/processes (different from cost)	
Avoidance of waste management costs and/or environmental damages costs (related to disposal of feedstock now used as raw materials for biobased products for instance)	
Possibility of additional profit generation for the raw material producers in bio-based value chains	
Demand of biobased product (volume of biobased products purchased in the region)	
Commercialisation of innovative technologies at national level	
Existence of investors (public investors, private investors, banks, venture capital, business angels, crowdfunding) active in the bioeconomy sector	

<p>Existent opportunities: Under-used resources that remain unexploited (the aim is to identify, for in-stance, if an end user in a region demands a bi-obased product which could be produced in the re-gion instead of imported since the regions accounts with the raw materials to produce it but maybe the technology required is not available, etc.)</p>	
<p>Number of employees (for each bioeconomy sub-industry, for all bioeconomy, for all regional econ-omy)</p>	
<p>Turnover (for each bioeconomy subindustry, for all bioeconomy, for all regional economy)</p>	
<p>Share of the bioeconomy in number of employees and turnover terms (share from all regional econ-omy)</p>	
<p>5. Transition towards bioeconomy. Using an interdisciplinary approach is key to define and assess the dimensions of the bioeconomy as a means of achieving sustainability from the industrial point of view. To this end, to move from fossil fuel industries to biobased industries is at the heart of the overall bioeconomy-related concepts in public, scientific, and political discourse. In regional policies, the evaluation of existing facilities and the adaptation to a new bioeconomy paradigm appears to be critical.</p>	
<p>Chemical, agro-food or other industrial companies that look for a shift from fossil resources to biolog-ical resources and bio-based products in the region or neighbouring regions</p>	
<p>Technology maturity of the industrial sector in the region (chemical industry, bioenergy, etc.)</p>	

Feedstock flexibility of conversion technologies in the region or neighbouring regions	
Number of consolidated industrial players, but also small and innovative young companies or entrepreneurs with the potential to stimulate innovation in the region or neighbouring regions	
'Close to zero' waste production initiatives/examples and/or number of bio-based initiatives in the region	
Existence and/or development of demonstration flagship technologies/biorefineries projects in the region	
Existence of non-operative/dismissed plants in the region looking for conversion into modified (bio-economy) plant	
Active and dynamic business/entrepreneurial community/ cross-sectorial trend for operation in the region (for example number of start-ups, existent companies' expansion process, etc.)	
Innovation culture among companies: willingness and capacity (since they are often small, do they focus on their core business or innovation is one of their strategic objectives)	
6. Public and institutional support/Governance/Policy framework: This is a prerequisite for investor confidence. Information regarding the existence of policies and programs for the development and channeling of entrepreneurial talent for increasing the effectiveness of entrepreneurs and demand for entrepreneurship is needed. Furthermore, the existing regulatory framework for facilitating the establishment of new entrepreneurship is of paramount importance.	

Existent supportive bioeconomy policy framework	
Policy correlation/coherence at regional and national level (Bioeconomy, rural development, etc. priorities/targets aligned at regional and national level)	
Cross-border and cross-regional collaboration/alliances (supporting regional and inter-regional projects of strategic importance for development of the bioeconomy sector)	
Supporting strategic partnerships between industries and enterprises in the region or among neighbouring regions	
Legislation/Regulations/Permitting process to facilitate implementation of initiatives (including for instance the reduction of the level of bureaucracy leading to lengthy administrative and approval procedures)	
Existent measures differentiating among regulations (imposed by law), financial support measures and soft measures (guidelines):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o fostering innovation; to promote industrial symbiosis o to support valorisation schemes o to support local value chains implementation o to facilitate the cooperation between government, research institutions and industry (including agriculture/forestry, harvesting, logistics, biomaterials, bioenergy, etc.) (for example collaboration agreements between industry-research institutions) o to optimise the innovation and knowledge transfer system (funding programmes targeting innovation and dissemination)

<p>Existent policies:</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Energy and climate policies o Circular Economy support policies To strengthen interactions and greater involvement of stake-holders o Policies supporting innovation in technology (focus on conversion process) o Policies focusing on the biomass supply such as forest, environ-mental and nature conserva-tion/sustain-ability policies, pro-duction close to zero waste poli-cies, policy aiming the imple-mentation of sustain-able rural and water management sys-tems, waste management pol-icy, etc.
<p>Existence of national bioeconomy strategy (includ-ing the corresponding Action Plan)</p>	
<p>Relevance of regional development planning</p>	
<p>Stability of the policies and policies duration sup-porting bioeconomy initiatives (to avoid uncer-tainty caused by changes in government which of-ten results on the cancellation of plans and pro-grammes established by the previous government without a broad political consensus)</p>	
<p>R&D budget (when it is reduced it is difficult for companies to access)</p>	
<p>7. Funding: It defines the current situation of the region in accessing both private and public funds and other kind of investment mechanisms, if existing. For example, private institutions interested to finance sustainable industrial projects or public budget to be invested in this kind of projects. In addition, it assesses the framework conditions to create an environment in which innovations can be developed, reach the market and become widely used.</p>	

Existence/availability of funding programmes targeting bioeconomy at national and regional level (specially for the commercialisation of bio-based technologies and products) supported for instance by European Investment Bank/Fund	
Establishment of mechanisms that enable feasible synergies and combination of different sources of funding	
Internal coordination among programmes	
8. Social and environmental aspects: Bio-based products and processes may produce impacts on society and environment. These impacts may occur along the entire value chain of bio-based products and can be linked to the production of biomass, to biorefinery processes, distribution or market uptake. Moreover, these impacts are in general specific for each region and can change over short periods of time which makes challenging to evaluate these aspects.	
Available skilled workforce (along the value chain: raw material collection and management, logistic, processing, distribution)	
Communications to society regarding bio-based activities (regular flow of information)	
Actions carried out to promote the change toward sustainable consumption	
Environmental awareness:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Information disseminated regarding GHG decrease achieved with bioeconomy initiatives/technologies o Resource depletion concerns o Others
Actions implemented in the primary sector in the region or neighbouring regions (already in place or expected in the coming 5 years):	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> o Contributing to reduction of greenhouse gases and other pollution o Strategy aiming for a 'zero waste' circular bio-economy im-

	plemented o To decrease the use of non-renewable fossil raw materials
Willingness to pay for bio-based products or/and consumer preferences towards bioproducts	
Feeling of the society regarding the participation and transparency of the regional/national administration	

Indicators from BIOMONITOR

Main Indicator	Sub Indicator	Possible measuring approach and suggested metric(s) ¹³	Sustainability dimension	Aggregation
1. Food and nutrition security				
Availability of food			Society	Economy wide
	Domestic food production	Food Commodities derived from bio-based ingredients (crops, meat, milk products, fish products, wild capture); Share of domestic agriculture production for food production in total available agricultural production (%)		
	Food imports			
	Food quality	Consumption in Kcal per capita per day from novel food products (e.g. veggie		

		burger - impossible food, bug-burgers, clean meat)		
	Development of new food products	New food products registered under novel food in different member states (number)		
Access to food			Society	
	Regional food purchasing power	Regional income per capita in linked with share of bio-based industries divided by Consumer Price Index for food		Regional
	Income per worker in bio-based industries	Real income per worker in bio-based industries divided by Consumer Price Index for food		Sub-sector
Utilization			Society	Sub-sector
	Improved food nutrition by better packaging material	change in shelf life and nutritional values		
	Nutritional value	change in nutritional value by food ingredients derived from bio-based products		
	Meat- or plant-based protein ratio	Land demand for the protein component of the diet or for the whole diet compared to total land available (ratio)		
Stability			Society	Sub-sector

	Import dependency ratio	For novel food and others; Grubel–Lloyd index for food items		
	Value of food imports over total merchandise exports	For novel food and others		
	Price volatility of food	For novel food and others; Derived from CPI basked for food		
2. Sustainable natural resource management				
Sustainability threshold levels for Bioeconomy Technologies		<i>Maximum Incremental Social Tolerable Irreversible Costs (MISTICs) as a measure for resilience (see appendix 1)</i>	Environment	Sub-sector
		<i>Reversibel and Irreversible Benefits and Costs</i>		
Biodiversity		<i>Rényi entropy; Mean Species Abundance</i>	Environment	Regional
	Forest biodiversity	<i>Volume of standing deadwood and of lying deadwood on forest and other wooded land (m3/ha); Number of threatened forest species, classified according to IUCN Red List categories in relation to total number of forest species.'</i>		

	Agrobiodiversity	<i>Number of livestock breeds; Number of crop varieties; Registered seeds for crops used for biomass production for industry; Number of threatened species in agricultural ecosystems, classified according to IUCN Red List categories in relation to total number of species in agricultural ecosystems</i> <i>Mean Species Abundance on agricultural lands</i>		
	Aquatic biodiversity	<i>Number of threatened species in water ecosystems, classified according to IUCN Red List categories in relation to total number of species in water ecosystems.</i>		
Main Indicator	Sub Indicator	Possible measuring approach and suggested metric(s) ¹³	Sustainability dimension	Aggregation
Land cover		<i>Share of total area, %</i>	Environment	Economy wide
	Forest area	<i>Ha in relation to total ha</i>		
	Agricultural area	<i>Ha in relation to total ha</i>		
	Surface water	<i>Ha in relation to total ha</i>		
Primary Biomass production		<i>kg; % for bio-based industry</i>	Economy	Economy wide

	Forests	<i>kg; % for bio-based industry</i>		
	Agriculture	<i>kg; % for bio-based industry</i>		
	Fisheries	<i>kg; % for bio-based industry</i>		
Sustainable resource use			Environment	Economy wide
	Sustainable forestry	<i>Ratio of annual increment and fellings in forests (%); Ratio of fellings and estimated maximum sustainable level of cuttings in forests (%)</i>		
	Sustainable agriculture	<i>Nitrogen use for agricultural production (kg/ha); Phosphorus use for agricultural production (kg/ha); Soil erosion (tonnes/ha); Ammonia, NOx and SOx emissions (ktonnes); Environmental impact quotient</i>		
3. Dependence on non-renewable resources				
Bio-energy replacing non-renewable energy		<i>MJ; Share of bioenergy in total energy use (%)</i>	Environment	Economy wide
	Biofuels	<i>MJ; Share of biofuels in total energy fuel use (%)</i>		
	Biogas	<i>MJ; Share of biogas total gas use (%)</i>		
Bio-material replacing non-renewable resources			Environment	Sub-sector

	Wood-based constructions	<i>m³; Share in total construction, %</i>		
	Bio-based textiles	<i>Tonnes; Share in total consumption, %</i>		
	Bio-based furniture	<i>Tonnes; Share in total consumption, %</i>		
	Bio-based plastics	<i>tonnes of oil equivalent; Share in total consumption, %</i>		
Biomass self-sufficiency rate		<i>potentially available quantity of biomass</i>	Economy	Economy wide
	Agricultural biomass	<i>potentially available quantity of biomass (tonnes)</i>		
	Forestry biomass	<i>potentially available quantity of biomass (tonnes)</i>		
	Aquatic biomass	<i>potentially available quantity of biomass (tonnes)</i>		
	Biomass from waste	<i>potentially available quantity of biomass (tonnes)</i>		
Material use efficiency			Economy	Sub-sector
	Material and waste recycling and recovery rates	%		
	Recycling rate of bio-based products	%		
	Circularity indicator	<i>To be developed in Task 3.7</i>		
Certified bio-based products		<i>Number; Bio-based content, %; Consumption</i>	Environment	Sub-sector

4. Mitigating and adapting to climate change				
Greenhouse gas emissions		<i>CO2 eq. tonnes</i>	Environment	Emission-sector
Main Indicator	Sub Indicator	Possible measuring approach and suggested metric(s) ¹³	Sustainability dimension	Aggregation
	Forest carbon emissions and removals	<i>Gross emissions and removals in CO2 eq. tonnes</i>		
	Agricultural GHG emissions and removals	<i>CO2 eq. tonnes per feedstock and land use type</i>		
	Energy and industrial carbon emissions and removals	<i>CO2 eq. tonnes</i>		
Climate footprint		<i>Using EXIOBASE</i>	Environment	Sub-sector
Climate change adaptation		%	Environment	Economy wide
	Diversity of tree species	<i>Area of forest and other wooded land, classified by number of tree species occurring</i>		
	Climate resistant crops in agriculture	<i>climate resistant crops as percentage of total agricultural</i>		
5. Employment and economic competitiveness				
Innovation			Economy	Sub-sector
	Innovation hurdle for different industries	<i>Additional benefits needed in percentage for each euro invested; total amount</i>	Economy	Sub-sector

		<i>of fixed (irreversible) investment needed.</i>		
	Number of patents submitted and sub-field	<i>Number and shares per subfield</i>	Economy	Sub-field
Investments		<i>EUR per year and sub-sector</i>		
	Private sector bioeconomy investments: R&D and others	<i>EUR per year and sub-sector</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
	Public sector bioeconomy investments/supports/subsidies. R&D and others	<i>EUR per year and sub-sector</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
	Establishment and Expansion of biorefineries	<i>Number; capacity; production; products (including by-products); resources use; people employed</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
	Internet of Things in bioeconomy	<i>Mobile Coverage (2G, 2.5G, 3G, 4G, 5G); Internet connection speed</i>	Economy	Economy
Value Added of the bioeconomy sectors		<i>EUR per year and sub-sector, Share of total economy</i>	Economy	Sub-sector

	Turnover of bioeconomy sectors	<i>Turnover in bioeconomy sector as share in total turnover of the sector (bio-based and fossilbased)</i>		
	Value-added of bioeconomy sectors	<i>Value added in bioeconomy sector as share in total value added of the sector (bio-based and fossilbased)</i>		
	Share of SMEs on value added	Numbers, Euros		
	Share of high-tech companies	Numbers, value added		
Comparative advantage			Economy	Sub-sector
	Terms-of-Trade of biomass	<i>ratio between the index of export prices and the index of import prices per biomass type</i>		
	Revealed comparative advantage of biomass	Belassa index: (export of biomass in MS(i)/total exports in MS(i))/(export of biomass in EU28 minus NL/total exports in EU28 minus NL)		
Production and consumption of non-food and feed bio-based products		<i>kind, quantity, turn-over</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
Import and export of bioeconomy raw materials and products		<i>EUR per year and sub-sector and country</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
Employment			Society	Sub-sector

	People employed in the bioeconomy sectors	<i>FTEs in bioeconomy sector as share in total FTEs of the sector (bio-based and fossilbased)</i>		
	Quality of employment	<i>Labour Productivity (FTE/value added) in bioeconomy sector</i>		
Policies				
	Policy-induced investment hurdles	<i>Additional reversible benefits needed to compensate for regulations expressed in percentage; fixed regulatory compliance costs.</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
	Regulatory measures	<i>GHG emission target;</i>	Economy	Sub-sector
		<i>Renewable energy shares target; Bio-based share target</i>		
	Training and education policies	<i>Qualitative</i>	Economy	Economy wide
	Country-level strategies	<i>Qualitatively</i>	Economy	Economy wide

Indicators from STAR ProBio

D2.1 Cluster	Scrutinized impact categories
Ecosystem quality (biodiv.)	Land occupation * species richness
Ecosystem quality (biodiv.)	Ecosystem services loss
Ecosystem quality (biodiv.)	Biodiversity endpoint

Land use	Soil quality index
Land use	•Biotic production
Land use	•Erosion resistance
Land use	•Mechanical filtration
Land use	•Groundwater replenishment
Land use	Fertile land occupation
Land use	Soil carbon deficit
Land use	Soil erosion / degradation
Water availability	Water use: User deprivation potential (deprivation- weighted water consumption)
Air quality	Particulate matter
Air quality	Photochemical ozone formation, human health
Climate change	Radiative forcing as Global Warming Potential (GWP100)
Climate change	GWP bio
Eutrophication	Eutrophication, terrestrial
Eutrophication	Eutrophication, freshwater (P)
Eutrophication	Eutrophication, marine (N)
Mineral and fossil resources	Resource use, minerals and metals: Abiotic resource depletion (ADP ultimate reserves)
Mineral and fossil resources	Resources depletion endpoint
Mineral and fossil resources	Phosphate use
Mineral and fossil resources	Cumulative energy demand
	Resource use,
Mineral and fossil resources	fossils: Abiotic resource depletion – fossil fuels (ADP-

	fossil)
Mineral and fossil resources	Organic carbon content (TOC)
Wastes	Marine plastic pollution risk
Wastes	Biodegradability
Wastes	Recyclability (and other EoL options)
Acidification	Acidification
Ecotox	Ecotoxicity, freshwater (USEtox)
Human health	Human toxicity, cancer (USEtox)
	Human toxicity,
Human health	non-cancer
	(USEtox)
Human health	Human health endpoint
Ionising radiation	Ionising radiation, human health
Ozone layer	Ozone depletion

Indicators from EU Bioeconomy Monitoring Dashboard

Criteria	Components	Indicator	Unit	Data availability
Food security and nutrition are supported	Availability	Agricultural factor income per annual work (AWU)	Index	x
		New food products (by sector)		
		New food value chains (by sector)		
		Total biomass supply for food purposes, including inputs	1000 t of dry matter	x

		Biomass directly consumed by EU citizens as food	1000 t of dry matter	x
Access		Prevalence of moderate or severe food insecurity in the total population, yearly estimates	%	x
		Average dietary energy supply adequacy		
		Food purchasing power	% of GDP	x
Stability		Daily calorie supply per capita by source	kcal/cap/d	x
		Indicator concerning food quality, or food safety		
		Animal welfare		
Utilisation		Gouvernement support to agricultural research and development (by sector)	€/cap	x
		EU's self-sufficiency rate on protein for feed		
		Import dependency ratio of food (Import/domestic production)		
		Value of food imports over total merchandise exports		
Sustainable trade for food is fostered	Economic impact of trade	Economic impact of trade in exporting countries of food (to EU)		
	Environmental footprints of trade	Environmental footprints in exporting countries of food (to EU)		
	Social impact of trade	Social condition in exporting countries of food (to EU)		
Ecosystem capacity to produce services is maintained or enhanced	Environmental quality	Biochemical oxygen demand in rivers	mgO ₂ / l	x
		Phosphate in rivers	mgPO ₄ / l	x
		Phosphorus in lakes		
		Nitrate in groundwater	mgNO ₃ / l	x
		Nitrate in rivers		
		Nutrients in transitional, coastal and marine waters		
		Exposure of forest area to ozone		
		Exceedance of air quality standards in urban areas		

		Percentage area of urban green space (or percentage of natural area within the city boundaries)		
Structural and functional ecosystem attributes		Landscape fragmentation Index		
		Share of High Nature Value farmland in agricultural area		
		Share of organic farming in utilised agricultural area	%	x
		Livestock density index	unit per ha	x
		Forest fragmentation and connectivity index		
		Deadwood		
		Share of forest area		
		Forest and other wooded land growing stock	1000 m3	x
		Ecological status of European waters		
		Fish stock biomass in NE Atlantic & Mediterranean		x
Species diversity and abundance		Common Farmland bird Index	Index, 2000 = 100	x
		Common forest bird Index	Index, 2000 = 100	x
		Grassland butterflies Index	Index, 2000 = 100	x
		Age and size distribution of commercially-exploited fish species		
Conservation status of habitats and species		Surface of marine sites designated under NATURA 2000	km ²	x
		Surface of terrestrial sites designated under NATURA 2000	km ²	x
		Conservation Status of European Habitats		
		Conservation status of grassland		
		Threatend tree species in forests		
Primary production sectors are managed sustainably	Pressures from forest management	Ratio of annual fellings (m ³ /ha/year) to net annual increment (m ³ /ha/year)		x
		Fraction of primary residues remaining in forest		

		Change in ecosystems extent: Forest and woodland		
		Land use / land cover type taken over by forest		
		Number of annual introductions of invasive alien species in forests		
		Certified forests		
	Pressures from Marine fisheries & aquaculture management	Nutrient discharge from fisheries aquaculture		
		Fishing mortality of commercially exploited fish and shellfish exceeding fishing mortality at maximum sustainable yield - North-East Atlantic	F/F_MSY	x
		Fishing mortality of commercially exploited fish and shellfish exceeding fishing mortality at maximum sustainable yield - Mediterranean & Black Sea	F/F_MSY	
		Number of annual introductions of invasive alien species in marine waters		
	Pressures from Freshwater fisheries & aquaculture management	Number of annual introductions of invasive alien species in freshwater		
		Size of aquaculture production units		
		Number of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture production units		
	Pressures on agroecosystems	Ammonia emissions from agriculture		
		Land use / land cover type taken over by agricultural land		
		Change in ecosystems extent: cropland & grassland		
		Number of annual introductions of invasive alien species in agroecosystems		
		Intensification of farming (share of low input farms in UAA)	%	x
		Sales of pesticides		
Ecosystem services contribution to human well-being is maintained or enhanced	Provisioning services	Biomass production in EU from primary production sectors: Agriculture	tonnes of dry matter	x
		Biomass production in EU from primary production sectors: Fisheries	tonnes of dry matter	x
		Biomass production in EU from primary production sectors: Forestry	tonnes of dry matter	x

		Roundwood removals	m ³ solid volume over bark	X
	Regulating services	Flood regulation (flood control, flow, demand, potential, unmet demand, monetary values)		
		Air quality		
		Net ecosystem productivity		
	Cultural services	Aesthetics considerations of nature		
		Recreational services (recreation, flow, demand, potential)		
Resource efficiency, waste prevention and waste-re-use along the whole bioeconomy value chain is improved	Resource efficiency (Material footprint)	Domestic Material Consumption (Biomass)	% of total Domestic Material Consumption	X
		Material Footprint (Biomass)	kg/\$ of GDP	X
		Land footprint in EU of EU consumption (for non-food&feed)		
	Energy efficiency	Energy productivity	€ per kg of oil equivalent	X
		Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption	%	X
		Share of renewable energy in gross final energy consumption of bio based industries or bioenergy industries		
	Biogenic waste prevention, re-use/recycling, and recovery	Cascading factor of wood resources - Share of secondary woody biomass used in material industry	% of woody biomass used in material industry	X
		Circular material rate	%	X
		Total energy supply from municipal waste		

		Recycling rate of municipal waste	%	X
		Biowaste generated by source: Household	kg dry	X
		Biowaste generated by source: Industrial and Agricultural	kg dry	X
		Biowaste generated by source: Total	kg dry	X
		Biowaste recovered by source: Households	kg dry	X
		Biowaste recovered by source: Industrial and Agricultural	kg dry	X
		Biowaste recovered by source: Total	kg dry	X
Food loss and waste is minimised and, when unavoidable, its biomass is reused or recycled	Food loss and waste minimization	Food waste along supply chain: Total	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Primary Production	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Processing and Manufacturing	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Retail and Distribution	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Consumption	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Cereals	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Dairy	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Eggs	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Fish	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Fruits	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Meat	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Oilcrops	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Potatoes	tonnes	X
		Food waste along supply chain: Sugarbeets	tonnes	X
Food waste along supply chain: Vegetables	tonnes	X		
		Food waste along supply chain: Cocoa and Coffee	tonnes	X
Sustainable production and consumption is promoted	Bio-based products environmental impacts	Environmental impacts based on product-based LCA and basket of representative products of the bioeconomy		

Consumption patterns of bioeconomy goods match sustainable supply levels of biomass	Consumption and demand for biomass and bio-based products	Import dependencies for energy (wood, biofuels, bioenergy)			
		Total biomass consumed for energy		X	
		Total biomass consumed for materials		X	
		Share of woody biomass used for energy	%	X	
	Production of bio-based products	Liquid biofuels production (bioethanol, pure biogasoline, biodiesel, bio jet kerosene and other liquid biofuels)			
		Biogasses (indigenous) production			
		Production of bio-based materials (plastics, textiles, chemicals)			
		Advanced biofuels production			
	Reduced dependence on non-renewable resources	Share of renewables for transport electricity and heating & cooling	%		X
		Total consumption of energy, including fossil-based			
		Share of wood-based constructions			
		Share of consumption of bio-based plastics, textiles and chemicals			
	Sustainable trade of non-food biomass is fostered	Economic impact of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)	Economic impact of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)		X
Environmental footprints of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)		Environmental footprints of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)			
Social impact of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)		Social condition of trade in exporting countries of non-food (to EU)		X	
The sustainability of urban centres is enhanced	Enhanced well-being and health of urban dwellers	Self-assessed satisfaction with recreational and green areas			
		Self-assessed satisfaction with living environment			
		Self-assessed satisfaction overall life satisfaction			

Climate change mitigation and adaptation are pursued	Climate change mitigation	net GHG emissions (emissions and removals) from bioenergy (absolute and relative vs. total sector emissions)		
		net GHG emissions (emissions and removals) from BBI (absolute and relative vs. total industrial emissions)		
		net GHG emissions (emissions and removals) from agriculture	Million tonnes of CO2 equivalent	X
		net GHG emissions (emissions and removals) from bio-waste (absolute and relative vs. total waste emissions)		
		GHG emissions from fishing and aquaculture		
		net GHG emissions (emissions and removals) from LULUCF	Million tonnes of CO2 equivalent	X
		Financial support to bio-based sectors (climate action)		
	Climate change adaption	Annual heating and cooling degree days		
		Crop yield (Winter wheat, Spring wheat, Grain maize and corn-cob)	tonne/ha	X
		Water exploitation index (WEI)	Pressures on renewable freshwater resources (%)	X
		Soil moisture (seasonal average)		
		Soil erosion / desertification		
		Soil organic carbon content		
		Adaptation in agriculture, share of farmers with CAP risk management tools (insurance)		

		Adaptation in agriculture, share of agricultural land under commitments to improve adaptation (ha)		
		Adaptation in agriculture, unsustainable water use: share of irrigated land under commitments to improve water balance		
		Adaptation in forest, # fire instances		
		Adaptation in forest, Burnt area		
		Adaptation in forest, natural disturbance events		
		Adaptation in fisheries, potential catch		
		MS Preparedness - Year of adoption of the National Adaptation strategy/Plan (NAS/NAP)		
		Adaptation, International Transboundaries effects - loss in GDP		
The sustainability of urban centres is enhanced	Enhanced resilience/adaptation to climate change for urban areas	City preparedness - # of cities signatories of COM - Adaptation		
		Investments in urban adaptation through nature-based infrastructures or EBA		
Economic development is fostered	Contribution of bioeconomy to economic development	Contribution of the Bioeconomy to GDP		
		Value Added per sector: Agriculture	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Forestry	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Fishing and Aquaculture	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-based textiles	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-based wearing apparel	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of leather	%	
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of wood products	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of paper and paper products	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-based pharmaceuticals	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-based plastics and rubber	%	X
		Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of wooden furniture	%	X

	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-based chemicals	%	x
	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-based electricity	%	x
	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-diesel	%	x
	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of bio-ethanol	%	x
	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of food	%	x
	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of beverages	%	x
	Value Added per sector: Manufacturing of tobacco	%	x
	GVA to turnover ratio		
	Economic productivity (GVA/unit of biomass)		
	Gross value added per person employed in bioeconomy	Apparent labour productivity [1000 EUR per person]	x
Value of raw and processed biomass, value added in bioeconomy sectors	Turnover in bioeconomy per sector	Million EUR	x
	Value-added per sector	Value added at factor cost in million euro	x
Exports of EU food and non-food biomass, processed goods and/or related technologies	Export value		
	Trade balance (net export)		
Comparative advantage	Terms-of-Trade of biomass (export/import)		
	Revealed comparative advantage of biomass (Balassa index)		
	Number of enterprises in bioeconomy		
	Bioeconomy SME birth & death rates		

Inclusive economic growth is strenghtend	Employment in bioeconomy	Persons employed per bioeconomy sectors	number of people	x	
	Working conditions related to bioeconomy	Occupation health and safety in bioeconomy sectors			
	Equality & Inclusiveness in bioeconomy sectors		Employment by age in bioeconomy sectors		
			Employment by educational level in bioeconomy sectors		
			Employment by gender in bioeconomy sectors		
			Income by gender by sector		
		Income distribution along bioeconomy value chains			
Resilience of the rural, coastal and urban economy is enhanced	Existing knowledge on bioeconomy technologies	Adoption of new bioeconomy technology by primary producers for both production and transformation levels			
		Rolling-out of pilot projects			
		Investment in TRL8-9 bio-based products			
Knowledge generation and innovation are promoted	Knowledge generation/(high level) education	% persons employed with 3 ^o education in bioeconomy sectors			
		Changes in University curricula (number)			
		Investment in higher education related to bioeconomy			
	Research and innovation		Number of patents by bioeconomy sectors		
			Investment in research and innovation (1000 eur)		
			Open innovation		
			New non-food products produced from primary sources		
	Number of research outputs in the field of bioeconomy				
Demand and supply-side market mechanisms and policy coherence between supply and demand of food and non-food goods are enhanced	Market mechanisms (e.g. prices, consumer awareness)	Market or consumers acceptance			
		Number of labelled or certified bio-based products			
	Resource competition among sectors of the bioeconomy and Biomass		Share biomass used by primary sector		
			Producer prices per primary production sector		

demand for new value chains		
	Distance to logistics hubs (territorial dimension)	
	Income of primary producers (fish& seafood landing income, agriculture households, forest owners)	

Results of the survey for each indicator

Indicators are listed in descending order of the level of importance (starting with the highest in dark green, ending with lowest in red) and the respective average level of measurability (highest level of measurability in dark green, lowest level of measurability in red).

ID	Indicator name	Importance	Measurability
C.5.2	Renewable energy share in the total final energy consumption	4.5	4.0
A.3.2	Deforestation	4.4	4.3
C.3.3	Contribution of bioeconomy sectors to GDP	4.4	3.7
C.3.4	Value added (bio-based sectors)	4.4	3.4
A.1.6	Material and waste recycling and recovery rate	4.4	5
A.1.3	Water resource savings	4.4	5
C.1.1	Domestic biomass production in agriculture, forestry, acuaculture/fisheries	4.3	3.9
A.2.9	Soil condition	4.3	3.6
A.1.2	Material Circularity for bio-based products	4.3	5
B.1.1	Consumer awareness: consumer acceptance	4.3	3.1
A.3.7	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	4.3	3.2
C.4.2	Job creation potential	4.2	3.2
C.2.3	Private and public spending on research and development	4.2	4.0

A.1.1	Fossil resources savings	4.2	5
A.1.4	Greenhouse gas savings	4.2	5
A.2.3	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	4.2	3.3
B.2.3	Household equality: Access to separate waste collection	4.2	3.7
C.3.2	Turnover of bioeconomy sectors	4.2	3.7
A.2.10	Food loss and waste reduction potential	4.2	3.3
A.3.6	Forests under management plan	4.1	4.1
C.2.4	Bio-based research and innovation activity	4.1	4.0
B.1.3	Education and knowledge : technical awareness	4.1	3.1
C.5.3	Import dependency ratio	4.1	4.0
C.1.5	Land cover: Agricultural area, forest area, aquacultural area	4.1	4.6
B.1.5	Participatory process: involvement to decision making	4.1	3.4
A.3.1	Climate change adaptation: Diversity of tree species	4.0	3.7
A.3.3	Forest biodiversity	4.0	3.7
C.1.4	Production and consumption of non-food and feed bio-based products	4.0	3.5
C.4.1	Employment in each group of bioeconomy subsectors	4.0	3.8
C.1.2	Biomass self-sufficiency rate in agriculture, forestry, aquatic	4.0	3.5
C.4.3	Quality of employment	4.0	2.8
C.5.1	Resilience to economic and social shocks/instability	4.0	2.5
B.1.4	Participatory process: social acceptance	4.0	3.3
A.2.11	Agro-biodiversity	4.0	3.5
A.1.5	Air quality: Particulate matter	4.0	5
A.2.8	Proportion of agricultural area under productive and sustainable agriculture	4.0	3.6
A.4.1	Aquatic biodiversity	3.9	3.6
B.2.1	Household equality: Access to renewable energy	3.9	3.6

C.1.3	Biomass net trade	3.9	3.6
B.1.2	Number of stakeholders from various stakeholder groups (i.e. public authorities, private business, NGOs, general public) involved in consultations	3.9	3.8
A.2.5	Nitrogen use	3.9	3.7
C.2.6	Certified bio-based products	3.9	4.0
A.4.2	Change in carbon stocks / Carbon sequestration	3.9	3.0
B.2.2	Income equality : costs of a nutrition basket at city/community level	3.9	3.7
C.2.1	Advanced biorefinery technologies	3.9	4.0
C.3.1	Terms-of-Trade of biomass	3.8	3.3
B.2.6	Human Health	3.8	4.0
B.2.4	Regional equality: rural versus urban development	3.8	3.6
C.2.8	New products in biomass sectors	3.8	3.1
A.2.6	Phosphorus use	3.8	3.7
A.3.5	Forest increments and fellings	3.8	3.6
C.2.2	Number of firms in the (sub)sectors	3.8	3.7
A.3.4	Forest fragmentation	3.7	3.6
A.2.7	Rate of organic farming	3.7	3.9
A.2.4	Climate resistant crops	3.7	3.4
C.2.5	Number of patents	3.7	4.2
C.2.7	Market share of goods certified by independently verified sustainability labelling schemes	3.7	3.3
A.4.3	Marine protected area	3.7	4.1
A.2.2	Area covered by protected habitat or species	3.5	3.8
A.2.1	Agricultural areas under Natura 2 000	3.5	4.2

B.2.5	Gender equality	3.2	3.3
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